

Recursion Operator Extensions of Term Algebras and their Standard Squashing

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Abstract

Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over a set of variables X . We introduce the concept of *extensions* of $\mathbf{T}(X)$, that add additional operators to the term algebra, and *squashings*, which map each of the newly created terms in the extended term algebra to a term in the original one. We define a particular kind of extension, the *recursion operator extension*, which allows us to express any recurring pattern in a term precisely and formally using a general recursion operator. We also define a squashing from the recursion operator extension back onto the original term algebra, the *standard squashing*, which unravels the recursion operator, and subsequently study the properties of recursion operator extensions and their standard squashing.

Contents

Contents	1
1 Introduction	3
1.1 Symbols used	3
1.2 Statement of theorems	4
1.3 Basic definitions	5
1.4 Proofs of well-definedness	7
2 Properties of extensions, squashings and substitutions	9
2.1 Naïve approach	9
2.2 Algebraic approach	20
2.3 Outlook: Categorical approach	24
3 Recursion operator extensions and the standard squashing	26
3.1 Formal definition	26
3.2 Properties	31
3.2.1 Basic properties	31
3.2.2 Equivalence classes of recursion depths, generalization to the natural numbers and resulting properties	39

4 Applications and Examples	57
4.1 General considerations	57
4.2 A simple example: Calculating the golden ratio	58
4.3 Observations on "big operators" of ABELian monoids	59
5 Acknowledgments	59
List of Figures	60
List of Tables	60
References	60

1 Introduction

1.1 Symbols used

Symbol	Meaning	Definition
$\iota: A \hookrightarrow B$	Inclusion map from A to $B \supseteq A$	[3, p. 5]
S_n	Symmetric group of degree n	[2, p. 30]
$\mathbf{T}(X)$	Term algebra over X	[1, p. 84]
$T(X)$	Universe of $\mathbf{T}(X)$	[1, p. 84]
$f_{\mathbf{T}(X)}$	$\sigma(f)$ -ary operator of (\mathcal{F}, σ) -type $\mathbf{T}(X)$ corresponding to $f \in \mathcal{F}$	[1, p. 84]
$\bar{\varphi}$	Homomorphism $\mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{A}$ induced by $\varphi: X \rightarrow A$	[1, p. 85]
\mathbb{M}	Set of all 1-tuples of elements in M	1.1
en_M	Enclosure map of M	1.2
$f \uplus g$	Union of the maps f and g	1.3
$f[x_0 \mapsto y_0]$	Overriding of x_0 by y_0 in f	1.4
$\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}$	Induced map of the substitution \mathfrak{S}	1.12
$t\mathfrak{S}$	Application of the substitution \mathfrak{S} to the term t	1.12
$\mathbb{X}^{\mathfrak{C}}$	Set of all non-variable terms	1.12
$\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$	Recursion operator extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$	3.3
$T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$	Universe of $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$	3.3
$\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^n t$	Recursion operator	3.5
q_X	Standard squashing of $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ onto $\mathbf{T}(X)$	3.6
$T(X)^{\mathfrak{C}}$	Set of all recursion operator extended terms in $T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$	3.6
$t \succ 0$	Existence of a predecessor of t	3.7
t^-	Predecessor of t	3.7
$\ t\ _{\succ}$	Natural cardinality of t	3.22
$t_1 \equiv_{\succ} t_2$	Natural congruence of t_1 and t_2	3.25
\bar{n}	Canonical representative of $[t]_{\equiv_{\succ}}$, where $\ t\ _{\succ} = n$	3.28

Table 1: Symbols used

Arrow	Meaning
\dashrightarrow	Map
\hookrightarrow	Injective map
\dashrightarrow	Surjective map
\hookrightarrow	Bijjective map
\longrightarrow	Homomorphism
\hookrightarrow	Monomorphism
\longrightarrow	Epimorphism
\hookrightarrow	Isomorphism
\Longrightarrow	2-(mono-,epi-,iso-)morphism
$\cdots\cdots\rightarrow$	Induction

Table 2: Arrows used in diagrams

1.2 Statement of theorems

Theorem 3.32. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$ and $s, n_1, n_2, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $n_1 \equiv_{\succ} n_2$, the following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} n_1 \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} n_2 \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\|n_1\|_{\succ}} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\|n_2\|_{\succ}} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} t \right). \quad (1)$$

Theorem 3.38 (Variable exchange theorem). For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$, the following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=s \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=s \end{array} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right). \quad (2)$$

Theorem 3.41. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, the following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n}_1 \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=\mathbf{P}^{\bar{n}_2} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{P}^{\bar{n}_k} \\ i=s \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\sum_{j=1}^k n_j} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} t \right). \quad (3)$$

Theorem 3.46. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $i_1, \dots, i_k \in X$, where i_1, \dots, i_k are distinct, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\})$, the

following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \quad \overline{n_2} \quad \dots \quad \overline{n_k} \\ \mathbf{P} \quad \mathbf{P} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{P} \quad t \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1}) \end{array} \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\prod_{j=1}^k n_j} \\ \mathbf{P} \quad t \\ i_k=s \end{array} \right). \quad (4)$$

1.3 Basic definitions

Definition 1.1 (Set of all 1-tuples). *Let M be a set.*

$$\overline{M} := \{(x) \mid x \in M\} \quad (\text{S1T})$$

Definition 1.2 (Enclosure map). *Let M be a set. The enclosure map of M is the map*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{en}_M: M &\rightarrow \overline{M} \\ x &\mapsto (x). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Enc1})$$

Analogously, its inverse is given by the map

$$\begin{aligned} \text{en}_M^{-1}: \overline{M} &\rightarrow M \\ (x) &\mapsto x. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Enc2})$$

Definition 1.3 (Union of maps). *Let A, B, C, D be sets with $A \cap B = \emptyset$ and $f: A \rightarrow B, g: C \rightarrow D$ be maps. The Union of f and g is the map*

$$\begin{aligned} f \uplus g: A \uplus B &\rightarrow C \cup D \\ x &\mapsto \begin{cases} f(x), & x \in A \\ g(x), & x \in B \end{cases}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{UnM})$$

Definition 1.4 (Overriding). *Let A, B be sets, $f: A \rightarrow B$ a map, $x_0 \in A$ and y_0 be a mathematical object. The overriding of f in x_0 by y_0 is the map*

$$\begin{aligned} f[x_0 \mapsto y_0]: A &\rightarrow B \cup \{y_0\} \\ x &\mapsto \begin{cases} y_0, & x = x_0 \\ f(x), & x \neq x_0 \end{cases}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Ove})$$

Definition 1.5 (Extensibility of a term algebra). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and (\mathcal{G}, τ) be a type. If and only if*

$$\mathcal{F} \cap \mathcal{G} = \emptyset \quad (\text{Ext1})$$

and

$$\mathcal{G} \cap X = \emptyset \quad (\text{Ext2})$$

apply, we say $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extensible and (\mathcal{G}, τ) is extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$.

Definition 1.6 (Extension of a term algebra). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and (\mathcal{G}, τ) be a type extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$. The (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is the term algebra of type $(\mathcal{F} \uplus \mathcal{G}, \sigma \uplus \tau)$ over X .*

Definition 1.7 (Squashability of an algebra). Let $\mathbf{A} := (A, F_{\mathbf{A}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) and $\mathbf{B} := (B, F_{\mathbf{B}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{G}, τ) . We say \mathbf{A} is squashable with respect to \mathbf{B} if and only if

$$\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{F} \tag{SqB1}$$

$$\tau = \sigma|_{\mathcal{G}} \tag{SqB2}$$

$$B \subseteq A \tag{SqB3}$$

apply.

Definition 1.8 (Squashing of an algebra). Let $\mathbf{A} := (A, F_{\mathbf{A}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) and $\mathbf{B} := (B, F_{\mathbf{B}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{G}, τ) , where \mathbf{A} is squashable with respect to \mathbf{B} . A squashing of \mathbf{A} onto \mathbf{B} is a map $q: A \rightarrow B$ with

$$q|_B = \text{id}_B. \tag{Squ}$$

Definition 1.9 (Trivial squashing). Let $\mathbf{A} := (A, F_{\mathbf{A}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) . The trivial squashing of \mathbf{A} is the map id_A .

Definition 1.10 (Substitution). Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X . A substitution \mathfrak{S} in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is a map

$$\mathfrak{S}: X \rightarrow T(X). \tag{Sub}$$

Furthermore, given a subset $A \subseteq T(X)$, a map $\mathfrak{S}': X \rightarrow A$ and the inclusion map $\iota: A \hookrightarrow T(X)$, we may for the sake of simplicity omit ι when considering the substitution $\iota \circ \mathfrak{S}'$.

Definition 1.11 (Trivial substitution). Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X . The trivial substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is the map en_X .

Definition 1.12 (Application of a substitution). Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and \mathfrak{S} be a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$. The substitution \mathfrak{S} induces a map $\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}: T(X) \rightarrow T(X)$ given by the restriction of its domain to \overline{X} and $\overline{X}^{\mathcal{G}} := T(X) \setminus \overline{X}$ respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}|_{\overline{X}}: \overline{X} &\rightarrow T(X) \\ (x) &\mapsto \mathfrak{S}(x) \end{aligned} \tag{ApS1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}|_{\overline{X}^{\mathcal{G}}}: \overline{X}^{\mathcal{G}} &\rightarrow T(X) \\ (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) &\mapsto (f, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_1), \dots, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_{\sigma(f)})). \end{aligned} \tag{ApS2}$$

For a term $t \in T(X)$, the application $t\mathfrak{S}$ is given by

$$t\mathfrak{S} := \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t). \tag{ApS3}$$

Definition 1.13 (Set of variables). Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and $M \subseteq T(X)$. The set of variables in M is the set

$$\text{vars}(M \cap \overline{X}) := \text{en}_X^{-1}(M \cap \overline{X}) \tag{SoV1}$$

$$\text{vars}(M \cap \overline{X}^{\mathcal{G}}) := \bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}(\{t_k\}) \mid (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in M \cap \overline{X}^{\mathcal{G}} \right\} \tag{SoV2}$$

$$\text{vars} M := \text{vars}(M \cap \overline{X}) \cup \text{vars}(M \cap \overline{X}^{\mathcal{G}}). \tag{SoV3}$$

1.4 Proofs of well-definedness

Lemma 1.14 (Well-definedness of the extension of a term algebra). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every type (\mathcal{G}, τ) extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$, the (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is well-defined.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and (\mathcal{G}, τ) be a type extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$. The sets \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are disjoint according to (Ext1), so the map $\sigma \uplus \tau$ is well-defined. Moreover, the sets \mathcal{F} and X are disjoint according to the assumption that $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is a term algebra, and according to (Ext2) the sets \mathcal{G} and X are disjoint. Thus, $\mathcal{F} \uplus \mathcal{G}$ and X are disjoint, which is a sufficient criterion for the well-definedness of the term algebra of type $(\mathcal{F} \uplus \mathcal{G}, \sigma \uplus \tau)$ over X . \square

Lemma 1.15 (Existence of a squashing between every two squashable algebras). *For every algebra \mathbf{A} that is squashable with respect to an algebra \mathbf{B} , there exists a squashing of \mathbf{A} onto \mathbf{B} .*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{A} := (A, F_{\mathbf{A}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) and $\mathbf{B} := (B, F_{\mathbf{B}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{G}, τ) , where \mathbf{A} is squashable with respect to \mathbf{B} . According to (SqB3), B is a subset of A , therefore there exists a map $q: B \rightarrow A$ which extends id_B . The map q already fulfills the requirement (Squ). \square

Lemma 1.16 (Well-definedness of the trivial squashing). *For every algebra \mathbf{A} , the trivial squashing of \mathbf{A} is well-defined.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{A} := (A, F_{\mathbf{A}})$ be an algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) . The algebra \mathbf{A} is squashable with respect to itself because

- (SqB1) is satisfied by $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$,
- (SqB2) by $\sigma = \sigma|_{\mathcal{F}}$ and
- (SqB3) by $A \subseteq A$.

Furthermore, id_A fulfills the requirement (Squ), since $\text{id}_A|_A = \text{id}_A$ applies. \square

Lemma 1.17 (Existence of a substitution in every term algebra). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , there exists a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X . Since for every variable $x \in X$, the 1-tuple (x) is a term in $T(X)$, \widehat{X} constitutes a subset of $T(X)$. Hence, the inclusion map $\iota: \widehat{X} \hookrightarrow T(X)$ exists and the composition $\iota \circ \text{en}_X$ already satisfies the requirement (Sub). \square

Corollary 1.18 (Well-definedness of the trivial substitution). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , the trivial substitution of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is well-defined.*

Proof. The claim directly follows from the proof of Lemma 1.17. \square

Lemma 1.19 (Well-definedness of the application of a substitution). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every substitution \mathfrak{S} in $\mathbf{T}(X)$, the map induced by \mathfrak{S} , that is $\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}$, is well-defined.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , $t \in T(X)$ and \mathfrak{S} be a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$. Let $t = (x) \in \widehat{X}$ with $x \in X$. Then follows:

$$t\mathfrak{S} \stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t) \stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \mathfrak{S}(x) \in T(X). \quad (5)$$

Now let $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}$. Thus follows:

$$t\mathfrak{G} \stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \widetilde{\mathfrak{G}}(t) \stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, \widetilde{\mathfrak{G}}(t_1), \dots, \widetilde{\mathfrak{G}}(t_{\sigma(f)})) \in T(X). \quad (6)$$

□

Lemma 1.20 (Well-definedness of the set of variables). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every set $M \subseteq T(X)$, the set of variables $\text{vars } M$ is well defined.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and $M \subseteq T(X)$. Clearly, $M \cap \widehat{X} \subseteq \widehat{X} = \text{dom en}_{\widehat{X}}^{-1}$, so $\text{vars}(M \cap \widehat{X})$ is well-defined. In particular, $\text{vars}\{t\}$ is well-defined for every $t \in M \cap \widehat{X}$. Let $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}$ and assume that the well-definedness of $\text{vars}\{t_1\}, \dots, \text{vars}\{t_{\sigma(f)}\}$ has already been proven. Then,

$$\bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}\{t_k\} \quad (7)$$

$$= \bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}\{t_k\} \right\} \quad (8)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV2})}{=} \text{vars}\{t\}. \quad (9)$$

We conclude:

$$\text{vars}(M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}) \quad (10)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV2})}{=} \bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}(\{t_k\}) \mid (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}} \right\} \quad (11)$$

$$= \bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{(f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}} \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}(\{t_k\}) \right\} \quad (12)$$

$$= \bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{t \in M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}} \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}(\{t_k\}) \mid (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \{t\} \right\} \quad (13)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV2})}{=} \bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{t \in M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}} \text{vars}\{t\} \right\} \quad (14)$$

$$= \bigcup_{t \in M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}} \underbrace{\text{vars}\{t\}}_{\text{well-defined}}. \quad (15)$$

Thus, $\text{vars}(M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}})$ is well-defined. By (SoV3), the set $\text{vars } M = \text{vars}(M \cap \widehat{X}) \cup \text{vars}(M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}})$ is also well-defined. □

2 Properties of extensions, squashings and substitutions

2.1 Naïve approach

When extending a term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$, we are introducing new operators to it while leaving all operators of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ as well as the set of variables X intact. Consequently, any term that can be expressed in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ can also be expressed in any extension of the latter. This superset property also allows us to formulate a squashing from the extension back onto the original term algebra. The essence of this paper is to leverage this fact by temporarily introducing new operators to an already existing term algebra (i.e. extending it) and subsequently squashing it back. The choice of the particular squashing enables us to express far more complex terms without permanently relying on more complex term algebras and without using any kind of informal notation, like ellipsis.

Lemma 2.1 (Superset property of the universe of an extension). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every type (\mathcal{G}, τ) extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$, we denote the universe of the (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ with $T_{\mathbf{E}}(X)$. It holds that:*

$$T(X) \subseteq T_{\mathbf{E}}(X). \quad (16)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , (\mathcal{G}, τ) be a type extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$ and $t \in \overline{X}$. The claim evidently holds, hence t is a variable and $\mathbf{T}(X)$ and the (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ share the same set of variables X . Now let $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \overline{X}^{\mathcal{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}$. Then follows $f \in \mathcal{F} \uplus \mathcal{G}$ and $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T_{\mathbf{E}}(X)$, thus $t \in T_{\mathbf{E}}(X)$ holds. \square

Lemma 2.2 (Squashability of extensions). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every type (\mathcal{G}, τ) extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$, the (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is squashable with respect to $\mathbf{T}(X)$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and (\mathcal{G}, τ) be a type extending $\mathbf{T}(X)$. The (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is by definition 1.6 of type $(\mathcal{F} \uplus \mathcal{G}, \sigma \uplus \tau)$. Hence the requirement (SqB1) is fulfilled by the fact $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{F} \uplus \mathcal{G}$ and (SqB2) by $\sigma = (\sigma \uplus \tau)|_{\text{dom } \sigma} = (\sigma \uplus \tau)|_{\mathcal{F}}$. The requirement (SqB3) directly follows by applying Lemma 2.1. \square

Remark 2.3. *For every type (\mathcal{G}, τ) , every (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ and every squashing q from $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ onto $\mathbf{T}(X)$, where $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ denotes the (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ with universe $T_{\mathbf{E}}(X)$, the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathbf{T}(X) & \xleftarrow{\iota} & \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{T}(X)) \\ & \searrow \text{id}_{T(X)} & \downarrow q \\ & & \mathbf{T}(X) \end{array}$$

Figure 1: Characteristic property of squashings between term algebras

The existence of $\iota: T(X) \hookrightarrow T_{\mathbf{E}}(X)$ and q follow from Lemma 2.1 and 2.2, respectively.

Obviously, squashing a term that has already been squashed has no effect, as squashings do not alter terms in their codomain. This statement applies more generally to any two algebras where one is squashable with respect to the other.

Lemma 2.6 (Induced map of the trivial substitution). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , the trivial substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ induces the map $\text{en}_X = \text{id}_{T(X)}$, i.e. $\text{ten}_X = t$ holds for every $t \in T(X)$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X and $t = (x) \in \widehat{X}$ with $x \in X$. It holds that:

$$\text{ten}_X \tag{23}$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}}_X(t) \tag{24}$$

$$\stackrel{t \in \widehat{X}}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}}_X|_{\widehat{X}}(t) \tag{25}$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}}_X|_{\widehat{X}}((x)) \tag{26}$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X(x) \tag{27}$$

$$= \text{en}_X \circ \text{en}_X^{-1}(t) \tag{28}$$

$$= t. \tag{29}$$

Now let $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \widehat{X}^{\mathbb{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}$. Then follows:

$$\text{ten}_X \tag{30}$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}}_X(t) \tag{31}$$

$$\stackrel{t \in \widehat{X}^{\mathbb{G}}}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}}_X|_{\widehat{X}^{\mathbb{G}}}(t) \tag{32}$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}}_X|_{\widehat{X}^{\mathbb{G}}}((f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})) \tag{33}$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, \widetilde{\text{en}}_X(t_1), \dots, \widetilde{\text{en}}_X(t_{\sigma(f)})) \tag{34}$$

$$= (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \tag{35}$$

$$= t. \tag{36}$$

□

Lemma 2.7. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , every substitution \mathfrak{S} in $\mathbf{T}(X)$, $i \in X$ and $t \in T(X)$, the overriding $\mathfrak{S}[i \mapsto t]$ is a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X , \mathfrak{S} be a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$, $i \in X$ and $t \in T(X)$. Then, $\mathfrak{S}[i \mapsto t]$ is a map from X to $T(X) \cup \{t\} = T(X)$ according to Definition 1.4 and thus fulfills the requirement (Sub). □

Apart from applying the trivial substitution to a term $t \in T(X)$ as is,

- overriding any variable $i \in X$ by itself first (i.e. applying $\text{en}_X[i \mapsto (i)]$) or
- overriding a variable $i \in X$ which does not occur in t first (i.e. applying $\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]$ with $t_1 \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$ and $t_2 \in T(X)$)

yields the same result t .

Example 2.8. *Consider the term $t := x^2 + \frac{y}{2}$ and the instructions "replace all instances of x with x " and "replace all instances of z with $2y$ ". Because replacing x by itself is trivial and z does not occur in t , these instructions have no effect.*

Lemma 2.9 (Substitution of a variable with itself). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$ and $t \in T(X)$, the following equation holds:*

$$\text{ten}_X[i \mapsto (i)] = t. \quad (37)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X , $i \in X$ and $t \in T(X)$. Because

$$\text{en}_X[i \mapsto (i)](i) \stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} (i) = \text{en}_X(i) \quad (38)$$

and

$$\forall j \in X \setminus \{i\} : \text{en}_X[i \mapsto (i)](j) \stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} \text{en}_X(j) \quad (39)$$

are true, the equation $\text{en}_X[i \mapsto (i)] = \text{en}_X$ holds. We conclude:

$$\text{ten}_X[i \mapsto (i)] = \text{ten}_X \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.6}}{=} t. \quad (40)$$

□

Lemma 2.10. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $t_1 \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$ and $t_2 \in T(X)$, the following equation holds:*

$$t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] = t_1. \quad (41)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X , $i \in X$, $t_1 \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$ and $t_2 \in T(X)$. It suffices to consider the restriction $\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]|_{X \setminus \{i\}}$, which itself is a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i\})$. Thus, the application $t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]|_{X \setminus \{i\}}$ is well-defined. It follows that:

$$t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \quad (42)$$

$$= t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]|_{X \setminus \{i\}} \quad (43)$$

$$\stackrel{i \notin X \setminus \{i\}}{=} \stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} t_1 \text{en}_X \quad (44)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.6}}{=} \text{id}_{T(X)}(t_1) \quad (45)$$

$$= t_1. \quad (46)$$

□

Let us shift the perspective to the substitute of a variable instead of the term we are operating on. Substituting a variable $i \in X$ with a term t_2 which does not encompass i , i.e. $t_2 \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$, clearly leads to i not occurring in the result, because all instances of i are being "killed" in the process.

Lemma 2.11. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $t_1 \in T(X)$ and $t_2 \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$, it holds that:*

$$t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \in T(X \setminus \{i\}). \quad (47)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , $i \in X$ and $t_2 \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$. Let $t_1 = (x) \in \overline{(X)}$ with $x \in X$. Then, it holds that:

$$t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \quad (48)$$

$$= (x)\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \quad (49)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2](x). \quad (50)$$

In the case of $x \neq i$, we have:

$$\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2](x) \quad (51)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} \text{en}_X(x) \quad (52)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Enc1})}{=} (x) \stackrel{x \neq i}{\in} \overline{(X \setminus \{i\})} \subseteq T(X \setminus \{i\}), \quad (53)$$

and in the case of $x = i$, we have:

$$\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2](x) \quad (54)$$

$$= \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2](i) \quad (55)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} t_2 \in T(X \setminus \{i\}). \quad (56)$$

Now let $t_1 = (f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}) \in \overline{(X)}^{\mathbb{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for $u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}$. It follows that:

$$t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \quad (57)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2}), (\text{ApS3})}{=} \underbrace{(f, u_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2], \dots, u_{\sigma(f)} \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2])}_{\in T(X \setminus \{i\})} \in T(X \setminus \{i\}). \quad (58)$$

□

Overridings of the trivial substitution possess the interesting property that they may either be nested or chained while providing the same result. Consider three terms $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in T(X)$ and a variable $i \in X$. It does not matter if we first replace i with t_2 in t_1 and subsequently replace i with t_3 or first replace i with t_3 in t_2 and then replace i with that result in t_1 . The statement becomes clearer if we use a more familiar notation: Let $\triangleright : T(X) \times T(X) \rightarrow T(X)$ with $(u_1, u_2) \mapsto u_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto u_2]$ be a binary operator on $T(X)$, which replaces i in some term in $T(X)$ with some other term in $T(X)$. Chaining two substitutions, as described earlier, would be written as $(t_1 \triangleright t_2) \triangleright t_3 = t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]$, while nesting the same substitutions would be written as $t_1 \triangleright (t_2 \triangleright t_3) = t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]]$. The operation of substituting an arbitrary, but fixed variable is therefore associative.

Lemma 2.12 (Associativity of substitutions of a single variable). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$ and $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in T(X)$, the following equation holds:*

$$t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]] = t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]. \quad (59)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , $i \in X$ and $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in T(X)$. For $t_1 = (i)$, it holds:

$$t_1 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]] \quad (60)$$

$$= (i) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]] \quad (61)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS1})}{=} t_2 \text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (62)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}),(\text{ApS1})}{=} (i)\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (63)$$

$$= t_1\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]. \quad (64)$$

For $t_1 = (x) \in \overline{(X \setminus \{i\})}$, where $x \in X \setminus \{i\}$, it holds:

$$t_1\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (65)$$

$$= (x)\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (66)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} (x) \quad (67)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} (x)\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2] \quad (68)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} (x)\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]. \quad (69)$$

For $t_1 = (f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}) \in \overline{(X)}^{\mathbb{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$, we assert that the claim has already been proven for $u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}$. Thus follows:

$$t_1\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (70)$$

$$= (f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)})\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (71)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}),(\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, u_1\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3], \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]) \quad (72)$$

$$= (f, u_1\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3], \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]) \quad (73)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}),(\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, u_1\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2], \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2])\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (74)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}),(\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)})\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3] \quad (75)$$

$$= t_1\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_2]\text{en}_X[i \mapsto t_3]. \quad (76)$$

□

The next lemma is purely an aid, which will prove useful in the following.

Lemma 2.13. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$, $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$, the following equations holds:*

$$\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t] \Big|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} = \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t] \quad (77)$$

$$\widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t] \Big|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}} = \widetilde{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]}. \quad (78)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. We first prove equation (77). Let $i \in X \setminus \{i_2\}$. It holds:

$$\text{en}_X(i) \stackrel{(\text{Enc1})}{=} (i) \stackrel{(\text{Enc1})}{=} \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}(i) \quad (79)$$

$$\implies \text{en}_X \Big|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} = \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} \Big|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} = \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} \quad (80)$$

$$\implies \text{en}_X \Big|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t] = \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]. \quad (81)$$

Because overridings do not change the domain of the map they operate on, the map $\text{en}_X \Big|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]$ still has the domain $X \setminus \{i_2\}$. We can therefore restrict the latter to $X \setminus \{i_2\}$ without changing anything and drop the first, redundant restriction:

$$\text{en}_X \Big|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t] \quad (82)$$

$$= \text{en}_X|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} \quad (83)$$

$$= \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} \quad (84)$$

$$\stackrel{(81)}{=} \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]. \quad (85)$$

This completes the proof for equation (77). We now proceed to equation (78) and first prove the following equation:

$$\widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}} = \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}}. \quad (86)$$

Let $u = (x) \in \widetilde{(X \setminus \{i_2\})}$ with $x \in X \setminus \{i_2\}$. It holds that:

$$\widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}}(u) \quad (87)$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]}(u) \quad (88)$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]}((x)) \quad (89)$$

$$\stackrel{(x) \in \widetilde{(X \setminus \{i_2\})} \subseteq \widetilde{(X)}}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{\widetilde{(X)}}}((x)) \quad (90)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t](x) \quad (91)$$

$$\stackrel{x \in X \setminus \{i_2\}}{=} \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}(x) \quad (92)$$

$$\stackrel{(77)}{=} \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t](x) \quad (93)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]}((x)). \quad (94)$$

Now let $u = (f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)}) \in \widetilde{(X \setminus \{i_2\})}^{\mathcal{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. Thus follows:

$$\widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}}(u) \quad (95)$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]}(u) \quad (96)$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]}((f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (97)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} \widetilde{(f, \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t](u_1), \dots, \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t](u_{\sigma(f)}))} \quad (98)$$

$$\stackrel{u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}{=} \widetilde{(f, \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}}(u_1), \dots, \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}}(u_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (99)$$

$$= \widetilde{(f, \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t](u_1), \dots, \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t](u_{\sigma(f)})} \quad (100)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]}((f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (101)$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]}(u). \quad (102)$$

This completes the proof for equation (81). We conclude:

$$\widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}} \stackrel{(81)}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t]|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}} \stackrel{(77)}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto t]}. \quad (103)$$

□

Instead of replacing some variable $i_1 \in X$ directly, we might first replace i_1 with an "auxiliary variable" $i_2 \in X$. This operation is not completely trivial, as i_2 must not appear in the term operated on. Otherwise, replacing i_1 with i_2 first and replacing i_1 directly may result in different terms.

Example 2.14. Consider the term $2x - y$. If we wanted to replace x by z , yielding $2z - y$, we can without any problems first replace x by some other variable w , so $2x - y$ turns into $2w - y$ and finally $2z - y$. It becomes problematic when we choose y as the auxiliary variable. In that case, $2x - y$ turns into $2y - y$ and finally $2z - z$. What were initially two separate variables have now become indistinguishable from one another.

Lemma 2.15 (Exchange of variables in overridings of the trivial substitution). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$ and $u \in T(X)$, it holds:*

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u] = \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u]. \quad (104)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$ and $u \in T(X)$. We observe:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u] \stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]}(t) \quad (105)$$

and

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto s] \quad (106)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto s]}(\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]) \quad (107)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto s] \circ \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(t). \quad (108)$$

We first prove the case $t = (i_1)$:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u] \quad (109)$$

$$\stackrel{(105)}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]}((i_1)) \quad (110)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u](i_1) \quad (111)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} u \quad (112)$$

and

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] \quad (113)$$

$$\stackrel{(108)}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] \circ \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}((i_1)) \quad (114)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] \circ \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(i_1) \quad (115)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u]}((i_2)) \quad (116)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u](i_2) \quad (117)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} u. \quad (118)$$

Next, we prove the case $t = (x) \in \widetilde{(X \setminus \{i_1, i_2\})}$, where x is an arbitrary variable in $X \setminus \{i_1, i_2\}$:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u] \quad (119)$$

$$\stackrel{(105)}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]}((x)) \quad (120)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u](x) \quad (121)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=} (x) \quad (122)$$

and

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] \quad (123)$$

$$\stackrel{(108)}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] \circ \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}((x)) \quad (124)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] \circ \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(x) \quad (125)$$

$$\stackrel{x \neq i_1}{\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=}} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u]}((x)) \quad (126)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u](x) \quad (127)$$

$$\stackrel{x \neq i_2}{\stackrel{(\text{Ove})}{=}} (x). \quad (128)$$

Thus, we have shown the claim for all $t \in \{(i_1)\} \cup \overline{(X \setminus \{i_1, i_2\})} \stackrel{(\text{S1T})}{=} \{(x) \mid x \in \{i_1\}\} \cup \{(x) \mid x \in X \setminus \{i_1, i_2\}\} = \{(x) \mid x \in X \setminus \{i_2\}\} \stackrel{(\text{S1T})}{=} \overline{(X \setminus \{i_2\})}$. Lastly, we prove the claim for $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \overline{(X \setminus \{i_2\})}^{\mathcal{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}$. Then follows:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u] \quad (129)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2}), (\text{ApS3})}{=} (f, t_1\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u], \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto u]) \quad (130)$$

$$= (f, t_1\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u], \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]) \quad (131)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2}), (\text{ApS3})}{=} (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u] \quad (132)$$

$$= \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]. \quad (133)$$

□

Corollary 2.16 (Back-and-forth substitution of variables). *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$, it holds:*

$$t = \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)]. \quad (134)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. It follows:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \quad (135)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.15}}{=} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_1)] \quad (136)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.9}}{=} t. \quad (137)$$

□

The next result is an occasionally useful combination of Lemma 2.12 and Lemma 2.15.

Lemma 2.17. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $t, u \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$ and $v \in T(X)$, the following equation holds:*

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] = \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v]. \quad (138)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $t, u \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$ and $v \in T(X)$. We first prove the case $t = (i_1)$:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v] \quad (139)$$

$$= (i_1)\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v] \quad (140)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v] \quad (141)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.15}}{=} u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (142)$$

and

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (143)$$

$$= (i_1)\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (144)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v]. \quad (145)$$

Next, we prove the case $t = (x) \in \overline{(X \setminus \{i_1, i_2\})}$ with $x \in X \setminus \{i_1, i_2\}$:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v] \quad (146)$$

$$= (x)\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v] \quad (147)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} (x)\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v] \quad (148)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} (x) \quad (149)$$

and

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (150)$$

$$= (x)\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (151)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} (x)\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (152)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} (x). \quad (153)$$

Lastly, we prove the claim for $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \overline{(X \setminus \{i_2\})}^{\mathcal{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}$. Then follows:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (154)$$

$$= (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v] \quad (155)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, t_1\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v], \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u]\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto v]) \quad (156)$$

$$= (f, t_1\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v], \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v]) \quad (157)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v] \quad (158)$$

$$= \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto u\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto v]. \quad (159)$$

□

Lastly, we prove the rather trivial fact that any term $t \in T(X)$ is indeed an element of the term algebra over the set of variables that occur in t . This can be generalized to subsets $M \subseteq T(X)$ and the set of variables that occur in any element in M .

Lemma 2.18. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and $t \in T(X)$, it holds that:*

$$t \in T(\text{vars}\{t\}). \quad (160)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X . Let $t \in \widehat{X}$. Then holds:

$$t \in \{t\} \cap \widehat{X} \quad (161)$$

$$\subseteq T(\text{en}_X^{-1}(\{t\} \cap \widehat{X})) \quad (162)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV1})}{=} T(\text{vars}(\{t\} \cap \widehat{X})) \quad (163)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV3})}{=} T(\text{vars}\{t\}). \quad (164)$$

Now let $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}$. Thus follows:

$$t = (f, \underbrace{t_1}_{\in T(\text{vars}\{t_1\})}, \dots, \underbrace{t_{\sigma(f)}}_{\in T(\text{vars}\{t_{\sigma(f)}\})}) \quad (165)$$

$$\in T\left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}\{t_k\}\right) \quad (166)$$

$$= T\left(\bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(f)} \text{vars}\{t_k\} \right\}\right) \quad (167)$$

$$= T\left(\bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(g)} \text{vars}\{u_k\} \mid (g, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(g)}) \in \{t\} \right\}\right) \quad (168)$$

$$\stackrel{t \in \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}}}{=} T\left(\bigcup \left\{ \bigcup_{k=1}^{\sigma(g)} \text{vars}\{u_k\} \mid (g, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(g)}) \in \{t\} \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}} \right\}\right) \quad (169)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV2})}{=} T(\text{vars}(\{t\} \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{G}})) \quad (170)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV3})}{\subseteq} T(\text{vars}\{t\}). \quad (171)$$

□

Corollary 2.19. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and $M \subseteq T(X)$, it holds that:*

$$M \subseteq T(\text{vars } M). \quad (172)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X and $M \subseteq T(X)$. It follows:

$$M = \bigcup_{t \in M} \underbrace{\{t\}}_{\substack{\in T(\text{vars}\{t\}) \\ \text{Lemma 2.18}}} \quad (173)$$

$$\subseteq \bigcup_{t \in M} \text{vars}\{t\} \quad (174)$$

$$= \left(\bigcup_{t \in M \cap \widehat{X}} \text{vars}\{t\} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{t \in M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{C}}} \text{vars}\{t\} \right) \quad (175)$$

$$\stackrel{(10)}{=} \left(\bigcup_{t \in M \cap \widehat{X}} \text{vars}\{t\} \right) \cup \text{vars} \left(M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{C}} \right) \quad (176)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV1})}{=} \left(\bigcup_{t \in M \cap \widehat{X}} \{\text{en}_X^{-1}(t)\} \right) \cup \text{vars} \left(M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{C}} \right) \quad (177)$$

$$= \text{en}_X^{-1} \left(M \cap \widehat{X} \right) \cup \text{vars} \left(M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{C}} \right) \quad (178)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV1})}{=} \text{vars} \left(M \cap \widehat{X} \right) \cup \text{vars} \left(M \cap \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{C}} \right) \quad (179)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{SoV3})}{=} \text{vars} M. \quad (180)$$

□

2.2 Algebraic approach

It becomes clear from the definition of applications of substitutions (Definition 1.12), in particular from equation (ApS2), that the maps induced by substitutions possess some kind of homomorphic property. To be precise, the induced map of a substitution is an endomorphism in the term algebra it operates on. More generally, it is an homomorphism to the term algebra of the same type over the set of variables that occur in the image of the substitution.

Lemma 2.20. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every substitution \mathfrak{S} in $\mathbf{T}(X)$, $\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}$ is an endomorphism in $\mathbf{T}(X)$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and \mathfrak{S} be a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$. We only need to consider terms in $\widehat{X}^{\mathcal{C}}$, because terms in \widehat{X} , i.e. variables, are not the result of the application of an operator. Let $(f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \widehat{X}^{\mathcal{C}}$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$. It follows:

$$\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(f_{\mathbf{T}(X)}(t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (181)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}((f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (182)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} (f, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_1), \dots, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (183)$$

$$= f_{\mathbf{T}(X)}(\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_1), \dots, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_{\sigma(f)})). \quad (184)$$

□

Lemma 2.21. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every substitution \mathfrak{S} in $\mathbf{T}(X)$, $\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}$ is an automorphism in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ if $\mathfrak{S}|^X$ is bijective and $\text{im } \mathfrak{S} = \widehat{X}$. In that case, the inverse of $\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}$ is given by*

$$\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}^{-1} = \overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X} \quad (185)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and \mathfrak{S} be a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$. Let $\mathfrak{S}|^X$ be bijective and $\text{im } \mathfrak{S} = \underline{X}$. We will prove that

$$\overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}} = \text{id}_{T(X)} = \tilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \overbrace{(\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X}. \quad (186)$$

Let $t = (x) \in \underline{X}$. It follows:

$$\overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t)} \quad (187)$$

$$= \overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}((x))} \quad (188)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \underbrace{\mathfrak{S}(x)}_{\in \underline{X}}} \quad (189)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \text{en}_X^{-1} \circ \mathfrak{S}(x) \quad (190)$$

$$= \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \mathfrak{S}(x) \quad (191)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{im } \mathfrak{S} = X}{=} \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \mathfrak{S}|^X(x) \quad (192)$$

$$= \text{en}_X(x) \quad (193)$$

$$= (x) = t = \text{id}_{T(X)}(t) = t = (x) \quad (194)$$

$$= \text{en}_X(x) \quad (195)$$

$$= \mathfrak{S}|^X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(x) \quad (196)$$

$$= \mathfrak{S} \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(x) \quad (197)$$

$$= \mathfrak{S} \circ \text{en}_X^{-1} \circ \underbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(x)}_{\in \underline{X}} \quad (198)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \tilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(x) \quad (199)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS1})}{=} \overbrace{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X((x))} \quad (200)$$

$$= \overbrace{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(t)}. \quad (201)$$

Now let $t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \in \underline{X}^{\mathfrak{G}}$, where $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$, and assume that the claim has already been proven for $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}$. Thus follows:

$$\overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t)} \quad (202)$$

$$= \overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}((f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}))} \quad (203)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} \overbrace{\text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \left((f, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_1), \dots, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_{\sigma(f)})) \right)} \quad (204)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} \left(\overbrace{f, \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_1), \dots, \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X \circ \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_{\sigma(f)})} \right) \quad (205)$$

$$= (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) = t = \text{id}_{T(X)}(t) = t = (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \quad (206)$$

$$= \left(f, \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(t_1), \dots, \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(t_{\sigma(f)}) \right) \quad (207)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{\cong} \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}} \left(f, \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(t_1), \dots, \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(t_{\sigma(f)}) \right) \quad (208)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{\cong} \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X((f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (209)$$

$$= \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}} \circ \text{en}_X \circ (\mathfrak{S}|^X)^{-1} \circ \text{en}_X(t). \quad (210)$$

□

Lemma 2.22. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , every subset $Y \subseteq X$ and every substitution \mathfrak{S} in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ with $\text{im } \mathfrak{S} \subseteq T(Y)$, $\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}$ is a homomorphism $\mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(Y)$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , $Y \subseteq X$, $\mathbf{T}(Y)$ be the term algebra of type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over Y and \mathfrak{S} be a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ with $\text{im } \mathfrak{S} \subseteq T(Y)$. For $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(Y)$, the following equation holds true:

$$f_{\mathbf{T}(X)}(t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \quad (211)$$

$$= (f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}) \quad (212)$$

$$= f_{\mathbf{T}(Y)}(t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)}). \quad (213)$$

We conclude for $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)} \in T(X)$:

$$\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}(f_{\mathbf{T}(X)}(t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (214)$$

$$= \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}((f, t_1, \dots, t_{\sigma(f)})) \quad (215)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{\cong} (f, \underbrace{\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_1)}_{\in T(Y)}, \dots, \underbrace{\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_{\sigma(f)})}_{\in T(Y)}) \quad (216)$$

$$\stackrel{(213)}{=} f_{\mathbf{T}(Y)}(\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_1), \dots, \widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}(t_{\sigma(f)})). \quad (217)$$

□

Corollary 2.23. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every substitution \mathfrak{S} in $\mathbf{T}(X)$, $\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}$ is a homomorphism $\mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(\text{vars im } \mathfrak{S})$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X and \mathfrak{S} be a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$. It follows from Corollary 2.19 that $\text{im } \mathfrak{S} \subseteq T(\text{vars im } \mathfrak{S})$. Thus, according to Lemma 2.22, $\widetilde{\mathfrak{S}}$ is a homomorphism $\mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(\text{vars im } \mathfrak{S})$. □

Lastly, we take a look at two special cases of overridings of the trivial substitutions, where we substitute one particular variable by another, whose induced maps happen to be surjective and bijective, respectively.

Lemma 2.24. *For every term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $\widetilde{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}$ is an epimorphism $\mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$ and $\mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$ be of the same type as $\mathbf{T}(X)$. Since

- $X \setminus \{i_1\}$ is a subset of X ,
- $\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]$ is a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ according to Lemma 2.7 and
- $\text{im } \overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]} \subseteq X \setminus \{i_1\}$ according to Lemma 2.11,

$\overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}$ is a homomorphism $\mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$ according to Lemma 2.22. It is left to show surjectivity. Let $t \in \mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$ and consider $\text{ten}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)]$, which is a term in $T(X)$ according to Lemma 2.7. It follows:

$$\overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(\text{ten}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)]) \quad (218)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS2})}{=} \text{ten}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)]\overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]} \quad (219)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Corollary 2.16}}{=} t. \quad (220)$$

□

Lemma 2.25. *For every set X with $i_1, i_2 \in X$, where $i_1 \neq i_2$, $\overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}$ is an isomorphism $\mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_2\}) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$.*

Proof. Let X be a set with $i_1, i_2 \in X$, where $i_1 \neq i_2$, and $\mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_2\})$ and $\mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$ share the same type. According to Lemma 2.24, $\overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}$ is an epimorphism $\mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$. Therefore, the restriction

$$\overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})} \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.13}}{=} \overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]} \quad (221)$$

inherits the homomorphic property. Following the proof of Lemma 2.24, we know that for any $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})$, the statement

$$\text{ten}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \in \overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}^{-1}(\{t\}) \quad (222)$$

is true. Because $T(X \setminus \{i_1\})$ is a subset of $T(X)$, t is an element in $T(X)$, and in combination with Lemma 2.11, we conclude $\text{ten}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. We refine statement (222) to obtain:

$$\text{ten}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \in \overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}^{-1}(\{t\}) \quad (223)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.13}}{=} \overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}^{-1}(\{t\}). \quad (224)$$

Therefore, $\overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}$ is an epimorphism $\mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_2\}) \rightarrow \mathbf{T}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$. It is left to show injectivity. For the sake of contradiction, assume that there exist $u, v \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$ with $u \neq v$, such that $\overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(u) = \overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(v)$ is true. It follows:

$$\overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(u) = \overline{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(v) \quad (225)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.13}}{\implies} \overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}(u) = \overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}|_{T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}(v) \quad (226)$$

$$\implies \overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(u) = \overline{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}(v) \quad (227)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{\implies} \text{uen}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] = \text{ven}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (228)$$

$$\implies \text{uen}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] = \text{ven}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \quad (229)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Corollary 2.16}}{\implies} \text{uen}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \stackrel{u, v \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}{\implies} u = v \stackrel{u \neq v}{\implies} \perp. \quad (230)$$

□

Remark 2.26. *Parts of the results of this subsection can be summarized in the following diagram, where $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is a term algebra over X , \mathfrak{S} a substitution in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ and $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$:*

Figure 4: Algebraic properties of substitutions

2.3 Outlook: Categorical approach

We could also approach this topic in a categorical sense, but because this is not necessary for the following sections, we do not want to open that Pandora's box and just give a quick overview.

Lemma 2.27. *For every algebra \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} , where \mathbf{A} is squashable with respect to \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{B} is squashable with respect to \mathbf{C} , and every squashing q from \mathbf{A} onto \mathbf{B} as well as every squashing r from \mathbf{B} onto \mathbf{C} , the composition $r \circ q$ is a squashing from \mathbf{A} onto \mathbf{C} .*

Proof. Let (\mathcal{F}, σ) , (\mathcal{G}, τ) and (\mathcal{H}, ν) be types and \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} be algebras of these types with universes A , B and C , respectively. Let \mathbf{A} be squashable with respect to \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{B} be squashable with respect to \mathbf{C} . We first prove that \mathbf{A} is indeed squashable with respect to \mathbf{C} :

- (Sq**b**1): $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{G} \wedge \mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{F} \implies \mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$.
- (Sq**b**2): $\nu = \tau|_{\mathcal{H}} \wedge \tau = \sigma|_{\mathcal{G}} \implies \nu = (\sigma|_{\mathcal{G}})|_{\mathcal{H}} \stackrel{\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{G}}{\equiv} \sigma|_{\mathcal{H}}$.
- (Sq**b**3): $C \subseteq B \wedge B \subseteq A \implies C \subseteq A$.

All that is left to show is that (Squ) is satisfied by $r \circ q$, i.e. $r \circ q|_C = \text{id}_C$. Let $c \in C$. It holds:

$$r \circ q|_C(c) = r(q|_C(c)) \quad (231)$$

$$\stackrel{B \supseteq C}{\equiv} r(q|_B(c)) \quad (232)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{\equiv} r(\text{id}_B(c)) \quad (233)$$

$$= r(c) \quad (234)$$

$$\stackrel{c \in C}{\equiv} r|_C(c) \quad (235)$$

$$\stackrel{B \supseteq C}{\equiv} r|_B(c) \quad (236)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{\equiv} \text{id}_B(c) \quad (237)$$

$$\stackrel{c \in C}{=} \text{id}_B|_C(c) \quad (238)$$

$$= \text{id}_C(c). \quad (239)$$

□

Lemma 2.28. *Let X be a set and $\text{Ob}(\mathbf{Trm}(X))$ denote the class of all term algebras over X . Then $\mathbf{Trm}(X)$ forms a category, where for any $\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X) \in \text{Ob}(\mathbf{Trm}(X))$, the hom-set $\text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X))$ is the set of all squashings from $\mathbf{T}_1(X)$ onto $\mathbf{T}_2(X)$ if $\mathbf{T}_1(X)$ is squashable with respect to $\mathbf{T}_2(X)$, and the empty set otherwise; the composition of morphisms is the composition of maps.*

Proof. Let X be a set. We conclude from Lemma 2.27 that compositions of morphisms are well-defined morphisms themselves. The associativity of the composition of morphisms follows from the associativity of the composition of maps. Furthermore, the trivial squashing of an object, which is the identity map over its universe, obviously satisfies bilateral neutrality. □

Lemma 2.29. *Let X be a set and $\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X) \in \text{Ob}(\mathbf{Trm}(X))$. Let*

$$\mathbf{Sqs}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X)) := \underline{\text{Hom}}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X)) \quad (240)$$

and

$$\text{Ob}(\mathbf{Sqs}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X))) \quad (241)$$

$$= \text{Ob}(\underline{\text{Hom}}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X))) := \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X)). \quad (242)$$

For any two morphisms $q_1, q_2 \in \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X))$, let

$$\text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(q_1, q_2) \quad (243)$$

$$:= \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Sqs}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X))}(q_1, q_2) := \{f \in \text{Ob}(\mathbf{Sqs}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X))) \mid f \circ q_1 = q_2\}. \quad (244)$$

Then $\mathbf{Sqs}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X))$ forms a hom-category, where the composition of morphisms is the composition of maps.

Proof. Let X be a set and $\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X) \in \text{Ob}(\mathbf{Trm}(X))$. For any $q_1 \in \text{Ob}(\mathbf{Sqs}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X)))$, the identity morphism is given by q_1 itself, because $q_1 \circ q_1 = q_1$ holds according to Lemma 2.4. For any $q_1, q_2, q_3 \in \text{Ob}(\mathbf{Sqs}(\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X)))$, $f \in \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(q_1, q_2)$ and $g \in \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(q_2, q_3)$, it holds:

$$(g \circ f) \circ q_1 = g \circ (f \circ q_1) = g \circ q_2 = q_3, \quad (245)$$

so $g \circ f \in \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{Trm}(X)}(q_1, q_3)$. The associativity of the composition of morphisms follows from the associativity of the composition of maps. □

Lemma 2.28 and Lemma 2.29 let us conclude that for a set X , the category $\mathbf{Trm}(X)$ can also be understood as a strict 2-category (more precisely, a $(2, 2)$ -category), i.e. as a category enriched over \mathbf{Cat} . Because all 2-morphisms of a squashing q in this new category are also 1-morphisms from the domain onto the codomain of q , we could repeat the process shown in Lemma 2.29 and construct $\mathbf{Trm}(X)$ as a strict n -category for arbitrary $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and even as an (∞, ∞) -category.

Remark 2.30. *Lemma 2.28 and Lemma 2.29 can be visualized using a diagram. Let X be a set, $\mathbf{T}_1(X), \mathbf{T}_2(X)$ and $\mathbf{T}_3(X)$ be term algebras over X , where $\mathbf{T}_1(X)$ is squashable with respect to $\mathbf{T}_2(X)$ and $\mathbf{T}_2(X)$ is squashable with respect to $\mathbf{T}_3(X)$. Let q_1, q_2, f be squashings from $\mathbf{T}_1(X)$ onto $\mathbf{T}_2(X)$ with $f \circ q_1 = q_2$ and r_1, r_2, g be squashings from $\mathbf{T}_2(X)$ onto $\mathbf{T}_3(X)$ with $g \circ r_1 = r_2$. The following diagram, which shows a snippet of $\mathbf{Trm}(X)$, commutes:*

Figure 5: The $(2, 2)$ -category $\mathbf{Trm}(X)$

3 Recursion operator extensions and the standard squashing

In this section, we introduce a means of extending almost any term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X to its respective *recursion operator extension* $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$, which encompasses new operators P_i for every $i \in X$ that allow us to formally abbreviate any recurring pattern of terms in $\mathbf{T}(X)$. We then define a squashing from $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ onto $\mathbf{T}(X)$ – the *standard squashing* q_X – which unravels all newly added terms back to terms in $\mathbf{T}(X)$.

The reason that we first extend a term algebra just to then squash it back is that this practice gives rise to a notion of semantics of our new terms relative to the "old", already existing terms. Usually, imposing semantics on a term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ means defining a map $\varphi: X \rightarrow A$ between its set of variables X and elements of another algebra of the same type \mathbf{A} , which in turn induces a homomorphism $\bar{\varphi}: \mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{A}$ (we call this homomorphism an *interpretation*). Note that one term algebra can have a multitude of interpretations. If we wanted to define the meaning of our new terms this way, we would first have to construct a new algebra of the same type as the extended term algebra. But if we first apply a squashing q to all terms in the extended term algebra, we may say that a new term t shall mean "whatever the term $q(t) \in T(X)$ means". The meaning of our new terms is therefore independent of the chosen interpretation.

Remark 3.1. *The following diagram aims to visualize the notion of "squashing before interpreting":*

Figure 6: Squash and interpretation in recursion operator extended term algebras

3.1 Formal definition

In order to extend a term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X by the operators P_i for every $i \in X$, we must make sure that X is non-empty (otherwise such an extension would be trivial) and that $\mathbf{T}(X)$ does not already encompass these new operators. Furthermore, we will need some notion of the natural numbers later down the road, so we demand that $\mathbf{T}(X)$ has a constant 0 representing the number 0 and a unary operator S representing the successor function.

Definition 3.2 (Recursion operator extensibility of a term algebra). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X . We say that $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is recursion operator extensible if and only if*

$$X \neq \emptyset \quad (\text{ROE1})$$

$$\forall i \in X : P_i \notin \mathcal{F} \quad (\text{ROE2})$$

$$\forall i \in X : P_i \notin X \quad (\text{ROE3})$$

$$0, S \in \mathcal{F} \quad (\text{ROE4})$$

$$\sigma(0) = 0 \quad (\text{ROE5})$$

$$\sigma(S) = 1 \quad (\text{ROE6})$$

apply.

All that is left to complete the definition of the recursion operator extension is the arity of our new operators P_i . For reasons that will be explained soon, we let it be three.

Definition 3.3 (Recursion operator extension of a term algebra). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be recursion operator extensible. Moreover, let $\mathcal{G} := \{P_i \mid i \in X\}$ and $\tau: \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ with $g \mapsto 3$. The recursion operator extension $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is the (\mathcal{G}, τ) -extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$. We denote the universe of $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ with $T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$.*

Lemma 3.4 (Well-definedness of the recursion operator extension). *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , the recursion operator extension $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ is well-defined.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be recursion operator extensible. Moreover, let the type (\mathcal{G}, τ) be defined in accordance to Definition 3.3. The requirement (Ext1) is fulfilled, since \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{F} are disjoint by (ROE2). Analogously, (Ext2) follows from (ROE3). \square

Definition 3.5 (Notation of the recursion operator). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$ and $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$.*

$$\mathbf{P}_{i=t_1}^{t_2} t_3 := (P_i, t_1, t_2, t_3) \quad (\text{NRe})$$

Now that we have defined the recursion operator extension of a term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$, we define a way of unraveling the newly added terms in $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ back to terms in $\mathbf{T}(X)$, i.e. a squashing from $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ onto $\mathbf{T}(X)$. This squashing, we call it q_X , should operate as follows: Consider a term $\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^n t$. We interpret n as the number of iterations or the recursion depth. Because n could itself be a term consisting of the recursion operator, we make sure to squash it first and then count the number of times the "successor operator" S occurs in $q_X(n)$; let us call this number k . Next, we apply the term t k -times to our start value s and return that result. Formally, this means replacing all instances of i in t by the result of the previous iteration k -times and treating s as the result of the first iteration.

Definition 3.6 (Standard squashing of a recursion operator extension). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be recursion operator extensible. The standard squashing q_X of $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ is a squashing from $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ onto $\mathbf{T}(X)$, defined by the restriction of its domain to $T(X)^{\mathbb{G}} := T_{\mathbf{P}}(X) \setminus T(X)$ with the following signature:*

$$q_X|_{T(X)^{\mathbb{G}}}: T(X)^{\mathbb{G}} \rightarrow T(X) \quad (\text{StS1})$$

$$u \mapsto q_X(u)$$

Let $u \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. If $\exists i \in X \exists s, n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X) : u = \mathbf{P}_{i=s}^n t$ holds true, we define a termination condition

$$\mathcal{A}(n) : \iff \nexists n^- \in T(X) : q_X(n) = \mathbf{S}(n^-) \quad (\text{StS2})$$

and the following definition applies:

$$q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^n t \right) := \begin{cases} q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)], & \neg \mathcal{A}(n) \\ q_X(s), & \mathcal{A}(n) \end{cases}. \quad (\text{StS3})$$

Otherwise, we write $u := (f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)})$ with $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)} \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, and the following definition applies:

$$q_X(u) = q_X((f, u_1, \dots, u_{\sigma(f)})) := (f, q_X(u_1), \dots, q_X(u_{\sigma(f)})). \quad (\text{StS4})$$

Definition 3.7 (Existence of a predecessor). Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X and $t \in \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$.

$$t \succ 0 : \iff \exists t^- \in T(X) : q_X(t) = \mathbf{S}(t^-) \quad (\text{ExpP1})$$

$$t \not\succeq 0 : \iff \neg t \succ 0 \quad (\text{ExpP2})$$

For a term $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $t \succ 0$, t^- denotes the predecessor of t , as can be taken from (ExpP1).

Remark 3.8 (on the notation t^-). For the term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , where $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is recursion operator extensible, and a term $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $t \succ 0$, the notation $t - 1$ for the predecessor of t was deliberately avoided, since it could be confused with a term in $T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, as long as $-$ denotes a binary operator in \mathcal{F} and 1 denotes a constant in \mathcal{F} or a variable in X .

It is worth noting that every term $t \succ 0$ indeed has one and only one predecessor, otherwise our definition would be ambiguous.

Lemma 3.9 (Uniqueness of predecessors). For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and every term $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $t \succ 0$, the predecessor t^- is uniquely determined.

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $t \succ 0$ and t^-, t' be predecessors of t . It holds that:

$$\mathbf{S}(t^-) \stackrel{(\text{ExpP1})}{=} q_X(t) \stackrel{(\text{ExpP1})}{=} \mathbf{S}(t') \quad (246)$$

$$\therefore t^- = t'. \quad (247)$$

□

Lemma 3.10 (Well-definedness of the standard squashing of recursion operator extensions). For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , the standard squashing q_X of $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ onto $\mathbf{T}(X)$ is well-defined.

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X and $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be recursion operator extensible. First, we note that $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ is squashable with respect to $\mathbf{T}(X)$ by Lemma 2.2. The restriction $q_X|_{T(X)}$ is already defined by (Squ), thus the claim holds for every $u \in T(X)$. We consider a term $u = (\mathbf{P}_i, s, n, t) = \mathbf{P}_{i=s}^n t \in T(X)^{\mathbf{G}}$, where $i \in X$ and $s, n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for s, n, t . Next, we make use of algebraic induction a second time

by treating $n \neq 0$ as the base case and subsequently assuming that the claim has already proven for the predecessor of n , if there is any. Let $n \neq 0$ apply. Then follows:

$$q_X |_{T(X)^c}(u) \tag{248}$$

$$= q_X |_{T(X)^c} \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) \tag{249}$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n \neq 0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X(s) \in T(X). \tag{250}$$

Now let $n \succ 0$ apply and assume that the claim has already been proven for n^- . It follows that:

$$q_X |_{T(X)^c}(u) \tag{251}$$

$$= q_X |_{T(X)^c} \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) \tag{252}$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n \succ 0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} \underbrace{q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right)}_{\in T(X)} \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.7}}{\in} T(X). \tag{253}$$

□

Remark 3.11. The calculation of q_X can be described through a flowchart diagram. The dashed arrows indicate recursion.

Figure 7: Recursive flowchart diagram of the standard squashing

Example 3.12. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, \mathbf{S}, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & \mathbf{S} & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$q_X \left(\overset{0}{\mathbf{P}}_{i=1} i + 1 \right) = 1 \quad (254)$$

$$q_X \left(\overset{\mathbf{S}(0)}{\mathbf{P}}_{i=1} i + 1 \right) = 1 + 1 \quad (255)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{S(S(0))} i + 1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (256)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^1 i + 1 \right) = 1 \quad (257)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{1+S(0)} i + 1 \right) = 1 \quad (258)$$

3.2 Properties

3.2.1 Basic properties

The first lemma of this subsection is purely an aid for the following proofs.

Lemma 3.13. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X with $i \in X$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \upharpoonright_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})} = q_{X \setminus \{i\}}. \quad (259)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X with $i \in X$. Let $u \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$. Then follows:

$$q_X(u) \quad (260)$$

$$= q_X \upharpoonright_{T(X)}(u) \quad (261)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{=} u \quad (262)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}} \upharpoonright_{T(X \setminus \{i\})}(u) \quad (263)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(u). \quad (264)$$

Now let $u = \prod_{j=s}^n t \in T(X \setminus \{i\})^{\mathfrak{C}}$ with $j \in X \setminus \{i\}$, $s, n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})$. Assume that the claim has already been proven for s, n, t . Assert $n \neq 0$. Then follows:

$$q_X(u) \quad (265)$$

$$= q_X \upharpoonright_{T(X)^{\mathfrak{C}}}(u) \quad (266)$$

$$= q_X \upharpoonright_{T(X)^{\mathfrak{C}}} \left(\prod_{j=s}^n t \right) \quad (267)$$

$$\stackrel{n \neq 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X(s) \quad (268)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s) \quad (269)$$

$$\stackrel{n \neq 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_{X \setminus \{i\}} \upharpoonright_{T(X \setminus \{i\})^{\mathfrak{C}}} \left(\prod_{j=s}^n t \right) \quad (270)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}} \upharpoonright_{T(X \setminus \{i\})^{\mathfrak{C}}}(u) \quad (271)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(u). \quad (272)$$

Now assert $n \succ 0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for n^- . Thus holds:

$$q_X(u) \quad (273)$$

$$= q_X|_{T(X)^{\mathfrak{c}}}(u) = q_X|_{T(X)^{\mathfrak{c}}}\left(\prod_{j=s}^n t\right) \quad (274)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(StS3)}^{n>0}}{=} q_X\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right) \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (275)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right) \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (276)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right) \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)] \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)] \quad (277)$$

and

$$q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(u) \quad (278)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}|_{T(X \setminus \{i\})^{\mathfrak{c}}}(u) \quad (279)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}|_{T(X \setminus \{i\})^{\mathfrak{c}}}\left(\prod_{j=s}^n t\right) \quad (280)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(StS3)}^{n>0}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}}\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)] \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)]. \quad (281)$$

It is left to show that the equality (277)=(281), that is

$$q_{X \setminus \{i\}}\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right) \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)] \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)] \quad (282)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i\}}\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)] \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)], \quad (283)$$

holds. To show this, let v, w be arbitrary elements in $\text{codom } q_{X \setminus \{i\}} = T(X \setminus \{i\})$. It follows:

$$v \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto w] \quad (284)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.13}}{=} v \text{en}_X[j \mapsto w]|_{X \setminus \{i\}} \quad (285)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(ApS3)}}{=} \widetilde{\text{en}_X[j \mapsto w]|_{X \setminus \{i\}}}(v) \quad (286)$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}_X[j \mapsto w]}|_{T_{\mathbb{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}(v) \quad (287)$$

$$= \widetilde{\text{en}_X[j \mapsto w]}(v) \quad (288)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(ApS3)}}{=} v \text{en}_X[j \mapsto w]. \quad (289)$$

In particular, for $q_{X \setminus \{i\}}\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right), q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t), q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s) \in T(X \setminus \{i\})$, it holds:

$$q_{X \setminus \{i\}}\left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t\right) \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)] \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)] \quad (290)$$

$$\stackrel{(289)}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}} \left(\underbrace{\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i\}) \\ \text{Lemma 2.7}}} \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)] \text{en}_X[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)] \quad (291)$$

$$\stackrel{(289)}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}} \left(\prod_{j=(j)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)] \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i\}}[j \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)]. \quad (292)$$

□

We now observe what happens to the standard squashings of terms of the form $\prod_{i=s}^n t$ in $T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ if we remove the variable i from t or s . If i does not occur in t , replacing it in every iteration has no effect. This becomes clear when we take a look at the flowchart diagram in Remark 3.11 again: If n does not have a predecessor, the result of the squashing is just always $q_X(s)$, otherwise, there is nothing to be replaced in $q_X(t)$, so the result is $q_X(t)$ regardless of n .

Example 3.14. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, \mathbf{S}, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & \mathbf{S} & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^0 1 + 1 \right) = 1 \quad (293)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{\mathbf{S}(0)} 1 + 1 \right) = 1 + 1 \quad (294)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{S}(0))))} 1 + 1 \right) = 1 + 1 \quad (295)$$

Lemma 3.15. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $s, n \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})$ with $n \succ 0$, the following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) = q_X(t). \quad (296)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$, $s, n \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})$ with $n \succ 0$. Assert $n^- \neq 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) \quad (297)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n^- > 0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (298)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n^- \neq 0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X((i)) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (299)$$

$$\stackrel{(i) \in T(X)}{=} q_X|_{T(X)}((i)) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (300)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{=} (i) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (301)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS1})}{=} q_X(t) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (302)$$

$$t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\}) \stackrel{=}{=} q_X |_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}(t) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (303)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} \underbrace{q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)}_{\in T(X \setminus \{i\})} \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (304)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t) \quad (305)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} q_X |_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}(t) \quad (306)$$

$$= q_X(t). \quad (307)$$

Now assert $n^- \succ 0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for $n^- \neq 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) \quad (308)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (309)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X((i))] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (310)$$

$$= q_X(t) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X((i))] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (311)$$

$$t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\}) \stackrel{=}{=} q_X |_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}(t) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X((i))] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (312)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} \underbrace{q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t)}_{\in T(X \setminus \{i\})} \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X((i))] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (313)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X((i))] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (314)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (315)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (316)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(t) \quad (317)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} q_X |_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}(t) \quad (318)$$

$$= q_X(t). \quad (319)$$

□

If on the other hand i does not occur in s , all instances of i will be replaced with a term free of i in the last step of computing $q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right)$, so the result will be free of i as well. Again, it helps to compare this result with the flowchart diagram in Remark 3.11.

Example 3.16. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, \mathbf{S}, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & \mathbf{S} & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=i+i}^{\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{S}(0))} i+1 \right) = i+i+1 + 1 \quad (320)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1+1}^{\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{S}(0))} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (321)$$

Lemma 3.17. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and $i \in X$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})$, $n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, the following statement holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) \in T(X \setminus \{i\}). \quad (322)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})$ and $n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. We assert $n \neq 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) \quad (323)$$

$$\stackrel{(StS3)}{=} \stackrel{n \neq 0}{=} q_X(s) \quad (324)$$

$$\stackrel{s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}{=} q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}(s) \quad (325)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s) \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.11}}{\in} T(X \setminus \{i\}). \quad (326)$$

Now, we assert $n > 0$. Thus follows:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right) \quad (327)$$

$$\stackrel{(StS3)}{=} \stackrel{n > 0}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (328)$$

$$\stackrel{s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})}(s)] \quad (329)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} \underbrace{q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto \underbrace{q_{X \setminus \{i\}}(s)}_{\in T(X \setminus \{i\})}]}_{\substack{\in T(X) \\ \text{Lemma 2.7}}} \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.11}}{\in} T(X \setminus \{i\}). \quad (330)$$

□

The combination of Lemma 3.15 and Lemma 3.17 allows for the following generalization. The corollary claims that under certain circumstances, *all* recursion operators over the same value in a chain of recursion operators, except for the last one, can be canceled out, which is quite a bold statement. The criteria that must be met are that all recursion-depths except the last one are non-zero, otherwise one of the recursion operators would yield its start value upon squashing, and that the variable iterated over does not occur in the start value of the last recursion operator.

Example 3.18. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, S, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & S & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=i+1}^{S(S(0))} \prod_{i=1}^{S(S(S(0)))} \prod_{i=i}^{S(S(S(0)))} \prod_{i=1+1}^{S(S(0))} i+1 \right) = q_X \left(\prod_{i=1+1}^{S(S(0))} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (331)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=i+1}^{S(S(0))} \prod_{i=1}^{S(S(S(0)))} \prod_{i=i}^0 \prod_{i=1+1}^{S(S(0))} i+1 \right) = 1 \quad (332)$$

Corollary 3.19. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s_1, \dots, s_k, n_1, \dots, n_k, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $s_k \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})$ and $\forall j \in \mathbb{N}_{<k} : n_j \succ 0$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_1}^{n_1} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) = q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right). \quad (333)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s_1, \dots, s_k, n_1, \dots, n_k, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $s_k \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i\})$ and $\forall j \in \mathbb{N}_{<k} : n_j \succ 0$. For $k = 1$, the claim is trivial. Now let $k > 1$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for $k - 1$. Because $n_1 \succ 0$ is true, n_1^- exists. Assert $n_1^- \neq 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_1}^{n_1} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \quad (334)$$

$$= q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_1}^{n_1} \mathbf{P} \prod_{i=s_2}^{n_2} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \quad (335)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1 \succ 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{\equiv}} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n_1^-} \mathbf{P} \prod_{i=s_2}^{n_2} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_2}^{n_2} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (336)$$

$$= q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n_1^-} \mathbf{P} \prod_{i=s_2}^{n_2} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (337)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1^- \neq 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{\equiv}} q_X((i)) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (338)$$

$$\stackrel{(i) \in T(X)}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{\equiv}} q_X|_{T(X)}((i)) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (339)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{\equiv} (i) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (340)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS1})}{\equiv} \underbrace{q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right)}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i\}) \\ \text{Lemma 3.17}}} \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (341)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{\equiv} q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right). \quad (342)$$

Now assert $n_1^- \succ 0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for n_1^- . Thus follows:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_1}^{n_1} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \quad (343)$$

$$= q_X \left(\prod_{i=s_1}^{n_1} \mathbf{P} \prod_{i=s_2}^{n_2} \mathbf{P} \dots \prod_{i=s_k}^{n_k} \mathbf{P} t \right) \quad (344)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n_1 > 0 \\ (\text{StS3}) \\ =}}{=} q_X \left(\overset{\bar{-}}{\underset{i=(i)}{\mathbf{P}}^{n_1}} \overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (345)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n_1^- > 0 \\ (\text{StS3}) \\ =}}{=} q_X \left(\overset{\bar{-}}{\underset{i=(i)}{\mathbf{P}}^{n_1}} \overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto (i)] \quad (346)$$

$$\text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)]$$

$$= q_X \left(\overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto (i)] \quad (347)$$

$$\text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)]$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.6}}{=} \underbrace{q_X \left(\overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right)}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i\}) \\ \text{Lemma 3.17}}} \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \quad (348)$$

$$\text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)]$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_X \left(\overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overset{n_2}{\underset{i=s_2}{\mathbf{P}}} \dots \overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (349)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_X \left(\overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) \text{en}_X [i \mapsto q_X(s_1)] \quad (350)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_X \left(\overset{n_k}{\underset{i=s_k}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right). \quad (351)$$

□

Due to the idempotence of squashings, it does not matter if we first squash s or t before applying q_X to the whole term $\overset{n}{\underset{i=s}{\mathbf{P}}} t$ or not, as demonstrated in the next two lemmata.

Lemma 3.20. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$ and $s, n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\overset{n}{\underset{i=q_X(s)}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right) = q_X \left(\overset{n}{\underset{i=s}{\mathbf{P}}} t \right). \quad (352)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$ and $s, n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. Assert $n \neq 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=q_X(s)}^n t \right) \quad (353)$$

$$\stackrel{n \neq 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X(q_X(s)) \quad (354)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.4}}{=} q_X(s) \quad (355)$$

$$\stackrel{n \neq 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right). \quad (356)$$

Now assert $n > 0$. Thus follows:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=q_X(s)}^n t \right) \quad (357)$$

$$\stackrel{n > 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(q_X(s))] \quad (358)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.4}}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (359)$$

$$\stackrel{n > 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right). \quad (360)$$

□

Lemma 3.21. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$ and $s, n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n q_X(t) \right) = q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right). \quad (361)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$ and $s, n, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. Assert $n \neq 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n q_X(t) \right) \quad (362)$$

$$\stackrel{n \neq 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X(s) \quad (363)$$

$$\stackrel{n \neq 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right). \quad (364)$$

Now assert $n > 0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for n^- . Thus follows:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n q_X(t) \right) \quad (365)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n>0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} q_X(t) \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(q_X(t))] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (366)$$

$$= q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(q_X(t))] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (367)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.4}}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=(i)}^{n^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (368)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n>0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^n t \right). \quad (369)$$

□

3.2.2 Equivalence classes of recursion depths, generalization to the natural numbers and resulting properties

Given a term $\prod_{i=s}^n t$, we are only interested in the number of predecessors of n , not in the actual contents of n . This allows for an important generalization by defining equivalence classes that contain all terms with the same number of predecessors. We therefore first need to define the notion of the "number of predecessors", which we call the *natural cardinality* of a term.

Definition 3.22 (Natural cardinality of a term). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. The natural cardinality $\|t\|_{\succ}$ of t is given by the following map:*

$$\begin{aligned} \|\cdot\|_{\succ} : T_{\mathbf{P}}(X) &\rightarrow \mathbb{N}_0 \\ t &\mapsto \begin{cases} 0, & t \not\succeq 0 \\ \|t^-\|_{\succ} + 1, & t \succ 0 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{NCa})$$

Lemma 3.23 (Well-definedness of the natural cardinality). *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , the natural cardinality $\|\cdot\|_{\succ}$ is well-defined.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. Assert $t \not\succeq 0$. Then holds:

$$\|t\|_{\succ} \stackrel{(\text{NCa})}{=} 0 \in \mathbb{N}_0. \quad (370)$$

Now assert $t \succ 0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for t^- . It follows:

$$\|t\|_{\succ} \stackrel{(\text{NCa})}{=} \underbrace{\|t^-\|_{\succ}}_{\in \mathbb{N}_0} + 1 \in \mathbb{N}_0. \quad (371)$$

□

Example 3.24. *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, S, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & S & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.*

$$\|0\|_{\succ} = 0 \quad (372)$$

$$\|S(0)\|_{\succ} = 1 \quad (373)$$

$$\|S(S(0))\|_{\succ} = 2 \quad (374)$$

$$\|S(1)\|_{\succ} = 1 \quad (375)$$

$$\left\| \prod_{i=1}^{S(S(0))} 1 + 1 \right\|_{\succ} = 0 \quad (376)$$

$$\left\| \prod_{i=S(i)}^{S(S(0))} S(i) \right\|_{\succ} = 3 \quad (377)$$

The next reasonable step is to define an equivalence relation based on the concept of natural cardinality. This equivalence relation, we call it the *natural congruence* relation, compares the natural cardinality of two terms for equality.

Definition 3.25 (Natural congruence). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X and $t_1, t_2 \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$.*

$$t_1 \equiv_{\succ} t_2 :\iff \|t_1\|_{\succ} = \|t_2\|_{\succ} \quad (\text{NCo})$$

If and only if $t_1 \equiv_{\succ} t_2$ is true, we call t_1 and t_2 naturally congruent.

Lemma 3.26 (Natural congruence is an equivalence relation). *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , the natural congruence relation \equiv_{\succ} is an equivalence relation.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X and $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. The relation \equiv_{\succ} is reflexive:

$$t_1 \equiv_{\succ} t_1 \quad (378)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{NCo})}{\iff} \|t_1\|_{\succ} = \|t_1\|_{\succ} \quad (379)$$

$$\iff \top, \quad (380)$$

symmetrical:

$$t_1 \equiv_{\succ} t_2 \quad (381)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{NCo})}{\iff} \|t_1\|_{\succ} = \|t_2\|_{\succ} \quad (382)$$

$$\iff \|t_2\|_{\succ} = \|t_1\|_{\succ} \quad (383)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{NCo})}{\iff} t_2 \equiv_{\succ} t_1, \quad (384)$$

and transitive:

$$t_1 \equiv_{\succ} t_2 \wedge t_2 \equiv_{\succ} t_3 \quad (385)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{NCo})}{\iff} \|t_1\|_{\succ} = \|t_2\|_{\succ} \wedge \|t_2\|_{\succ} = \|t_3\|_{\succ} \quad (386)$$

$$\implies \|t_1\|_{\succ} = \|t_3\|_{\succ} \quad (387)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{NCo})}{\iff} t_1 \equiv_{\succ} t_3. \quad (388)$$

□

Example 3.27. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, S, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & S & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$S(0) \equiv_{\succ} S(1) \quad (389)$$

$$S(0) \not\equiv_{\succ} S(S(0)) \quad (390)$$

$$\prod_{i=S(i)}^{S(S(0))} S(i) \equiv_{\succ} S(S(S(1 + 1 + 0))) \quad (391)$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{S(S(S(0)))} i+1 \equiv_{\succ} 0 \quad (392)$$

With the definition of an equivalence relation come equivalence classes. In the case of the natural congruence relation, such an equivalence class, we call it a *natural congruence class*, contains all terms of the same natural congruence, as desired. To simplify our work with said natural congruence classes, we pick a "simplest" representative of each class and call it the *canonical representative*. For the natural congruence class of terms of natural cardinality $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, the canonical representative shall just be the successor operator S applied n -times to the zero-constant 0 , very similar to PEANO's construction of the natural numbers.

Definition 3.28 (Canonical representative of a natural congruence class). *Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. The canonical representative $\overline{\|t\|_{\succ}}$ of the natural congruence class $[t]_{\equiv_{\succ}}$ is defined as follows:*

$$\overline{\|t\|_{\succ}} := S^{\|t\|_{\succ}}(0). \quad (\text{CRe})$$

Lemma 3.29 (Well-definedness of the canonical representative of a natural congruence class). *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, the canonical representative $\overline{\|t\|_{\succ}}$ of $[t]_{\equiv_{\succ}}$ is well-defined.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. To prove the well-definedness of $\overline{\|t\|_{\succ}}$, we have to show $\overline{\|t\|_{\succ}} \in [t]_{\equiv_{\succ}}$, i.e. $\overline{\|\overline{\|t\|_{\succ}}\|_{\succ}} = \|t\|_{\succ}$. Let $n := \|t\|_{\succ}$ and assert $n = 0$. Then holds:

$$\|\overline{n}\|_{\succ} = \|\overline{0}\|_{\succ} \quad (393)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{CRe})}{=} \|S^0(0)\|_{\succ} = \|0\|_{\succ} \quad (394)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{0 \neq 0 \\ (\text{NCa})}}{=} 0 = n. \quad (395)$$

Now assert $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for n . Thus follows:

$$\|\overline{n+1}\|_{\succ} \quad (396)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{CRe})}{=} \|S^{n+1}(0)\|_{\succ} \quad (397)$$

$$= \|S(S^n(0))\|_{\succ} \quad (398)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{S(S^n(0)) \succ 0 \\ (\text{NCa})}}{=} \|S^n(0)\|_{\succ} + 1 \quad (399)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{CRe})}{=} \|\overline{n}\|_{\succ} + 1 \quad (400)$$

$$= n + 1. \quad (401)$$

□

Example 3.30. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, S, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & S & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$\overline{\|S(S(1+1))\|_{\succ}} = S(S(0)) \quad (402)$$

$$\bar{4} = S(S(S(S(0)))) \quad (403)$$

$$\overline{\prod_{i=S(i)}^{S(S(0))} S(i)} = S(S(S(0))) \quad (404)$$

$$\overline{\prod_{i=1}^{S(S(0))} i+1} = 0 \quad (405)$$

$$\overline{S(S(\bar{0}))} = S(S(S(0))) \quad (406)$$

The first theorem of this paper states that two terms of the form $\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^n t$, which only differ in n and are otherwise identical, share the same image under q_X as long as their recursion depths lie in the same natural congruence class. This allows us to replace the recursion depth of such a term with *any* term in the same natural congruence class, in particular with the canonical representative of said class. We therefore just need to consider canonical representatives as recursion depths in proofs, which gives rise to the notion of natural numbers as recursion depths, as any canonical representative is induced by a natural number.

Example 3.31. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, S, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & S & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{S(S(0))} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (407)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{S(S(1+1+1))} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (408)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{\bar{2}} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (409)$$

Theorem 3.32. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$ and $s, n_1, n_2, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $n_1 \equiv_{\succ} n_2$, the following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^{n_1} t \right) = q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^{n_2} t \right) = q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^{\overline{\|n_1\|_{\succ}}} t \right) = q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^{\overline{\|n_2\|_{\succ}}} t \right). \quad (410)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$ and $s, n_1, n_2, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $n_1 \equiv_{\succ} n_2$. Assert $n_1 \neq 0$. Therefore, $n_1 \in [\bar{0}]_{\equiv_{\succ}}$ and thus $n_2 \in [\bar{0}]_{\equiv_{\succ}}$ and $n_2 \neq 0$ apply. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=s}^{n_1} t \right) \quad (411)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1 \succ 0}{\underset{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X(s) \quad (412)$$

$$\stackrel{n_2 \succ 0}{\underset{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{n_2} t \right). \quad (413)$$

Now assert $n_1 \succ 0$. Then holds:

$$n_1 \equiv_{\succ} n_2 \stackrel{(\text{NCo})}{\iff} \|n_1\|_{\succ} = \|n_2\|_{\succ} \stackrel{(\text{NCa})}{\iff} \|n_1^-\|_{\succ} + 1 = \|n_2^-\|_{\succ} + 1 \quad (414)$$

$$\therefore \|n_1^-\|_{\succ} = \|n_2^-\|_{\succ} \stackrel{(\text{NCo})}{\iff} n_1^- \equiv_{\succ} n_2^-. \quad (415)$$

Assume that the claim has already been shown for n_1^- . Then follows:

$$q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{n_1} t \right) \quad (416)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1 \succ 0}{\underset{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i_1=(i_1)}^{n_1^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (417)$$

$$\stackrel{(415)}{\underset{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i_1=(i_1)}^{n_2^-} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (418)$$

$$\stackrel{n_2 \succ 0}{\underset{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{n_2} t \right). \quad (419)$$

Because $\overline{\|n_1\|_{\succ}} \equiv_{\succ} n_1 \equiv_{\succ} n_2 \equiv_{\succ} \overline{\|n_2\|_{\succ}}$ applies, the following equation follows from what we have just proven:

$$q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{n_1} t \right) = q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{n_2} t \right) = q_X \left(\overline{\|n_1\|_{\succ}} \mathbf{P}_{i=s} t \right) = q_X \left(\overline{\|n_2\|_{\succ}} \mathbf{P}_{i=s} t \right). \quad (420)$$

□

Remark 3.33. *The generalization of recursion depths to the natural numbers allows for the creation of a new, iterative flowchart diagram of the computation of q_X , as opposed to the recursive one demonstrated in Remark 3.11.*

Figure 8: Iterative flowchart diagram of the standard squashing

The following lemmata help to prove Theorem 3.38, which roughly states that in a term of the form $\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^n t$, we can replace i in t by another variable, as long as we adjust the variable we iterate over accordingly and t is a term in $T(X)$. First, we observe that replacing a variable by another in a canonical representative – which are free of variables – has no effect.

Lemma 3.34. *For every recursion extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, the following equation holds:*

$$\bar{n} = \bar{n}\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]. \quad (421)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion extensible term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Then holds:

$$\bar{n}\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (422)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{CRe})}{=} \underbrace{\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{0})}_{\in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (423)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} \mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{0}) \quad (424)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{CRe})}{=} \bar{n}. \quad (425)$$

□

Secondly, we prove the following rewriting rules.

Lemma 3.35. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right). \quad (426)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})$. Assert $n = 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (427)$$

$$\stackrel{\stackrel{n=0}{(\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X((i_1))\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (428)$$

$$\stackrel{(i_1) \in T(X)}{=} q_X|_{T(X)}((i_1))\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (429)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{=} (i_1)\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (430)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS1})}{=} \underbrace{(i_2)}_{\in T(X)} \quad (431)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{=} q_X|_{T(X)}((i_2)) \quad (432)$$

$$= q_X((i_2)) \quad (433)$$

$$\stackrel{\stackrel{n=0}{(\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right). \quad (434)$$

Now assert $n > 0$. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \quad (435)$$

$$\stackrel{\stackrel{n>0}{(\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(t)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X((i_2))] \quad (436)$$

$$\stackrel{(i_2) \in T(X)}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(t)]\text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X|_{T(X)}((i_2))] \quad (437)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(Squ)}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (438)$$

$$\stackrel{t, (i_2) \in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})}{=} q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})}(t)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (439)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} \underbrace{q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right)}_{\in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \text{en}_X \left[\underbrace{i_2}_{\in X \setminus \{i_1\}} \mapsto \underbrace{q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}}(t)}_{\in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \right] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (440)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.15}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}}(t)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (441)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})}(t)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (442)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto \underbrace{(i_1)}_{\in T(X)}] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (443)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(Squ)}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X|_{T(X)}((i_1))] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (444)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X((i_1))] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (445)$$

$$\stackrel{\stackrel{n > 0}{\text{(StS3)}}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]. \quad (446)$$

□

Corollary 3.36. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] = q_X \left(\left[\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right). \quad (447)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_1\})$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \quad (448)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.35}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_2) \end{array} t \right) \quad (449)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS1})}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \end{array} t \right) \quad (450)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.34}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_1) \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \end{array} t \right) \quad (451)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.10}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_1) \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \end{array} \text{ten}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \quad (452)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS2})}{=} q_X \left(\left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right] \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right). \quad (453)$$

□

We have now done all of the necessary preparatory work to prove the second theorem. It states that for a term $\mathbf{P}_{i_1=s}^n t$ with the important restriction that t is a term in $T(X)$, not $T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, and that i_2 does not occur in t , so $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$, we may replace the iteration variable i_1 with i_2 without affecting the image under q_X as long as we adjust t accordingly, i.e. replace i_1 with i_2 in t .

Example 3.37. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, S, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & S & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$ over $X := \{i, j\}$.

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=1 \end{array} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (454)$$

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ j=1 \end{array} j+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (455)$$

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=1 \end{array} i+j+1 \right) = 1 + j + 1 + j + 1 \quad (456)$$

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ j=1 \end{array} j+j+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (457)$$

Theorem 3.38 (Variable exchange theorem). *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=s \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=s \end{array} \text{ten}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right). \quad (458)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra over some type (\mathcal{F}, σ) over X , $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be recursion operator extensible, $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. Assert $n = 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=s \end{array} t \right) \quad (459)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n=0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X(s) \quad (460)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n=0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \bar{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_2=s \end{array} \text{ten}_X [i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right). \quad (461)$$

Now assert $n > 0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for $n - 1$. Then follows:

$$q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_1=s}^{\bar{n}} t \right) \quad (462)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n>0 \\ \text{(StS3)}}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_1=(i_1)}^{\bar{n}-1} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (463)$$

$$= q_X \left(\underbrace{\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_1)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i_2\}) \\ \text{Lemma 3.17}}} \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (464)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Corollary 2.16}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_1)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (465)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.35}}{=} q_X \left(\underbrace{\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}_{\in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (466)$$

$$= q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (467)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (468)$$

$$\stackrel{t \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\}) \subset T(X)}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X|_{T(X)}(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (469)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(Squ)}}{=} \underbrace{q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto t] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)]}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i_1\}) \\ \in T(X \setminus \{i_2\}) \\ \text{Lemma 2.11}}} \quad (470)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.17}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\bar{n}-1} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto (i_1)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (471)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.15}}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\prod_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\overline{n-1}} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto \underbrace{\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)]}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i_1\}) \subset T(X) \\ \text{Lemma 2.11}}}]] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (472)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{=} q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\prod_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\overline{n-1}} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X|_{T(X)}(\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)])] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (473)$$

$$= q_{X \setminus \{i_1\}} \left(\prod_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\overline{n-1}} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)])] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (474)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} q_X|_{T_{\mathbb{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})} \left(\prod_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\overline{n-1}} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)])] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (475)$$

$$= q_X \left(\prod_{i_2=(i_2)}^{\overline{n-1}} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(\text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)])] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (476)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n>0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\prod_{i_2=s}^{\overline{n}} \text{ten}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \right). \quad (477)$$

□

The last two theorems of this paper, Theorem 3.41 and Theorem 3.46, provide a way of simplifying nested recursion operator terms $\mathbb{P}_{i=s}^n t$ to a term containing just a single recursion operator by

- adding the recursion depths if the nesting happens inside s or
- multiplying the recursion depths if the nesting happens inside t .

The commutativity of nested recursion operators then follows directly from the commutativity of addition and multiplication.

We first prove a simpler version of Theorem 3.41 which considers a single nested recursion operator in the start value and later use it in the inductive step of the main theorem.

Example 3.39. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, \mathbb{S}, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & \mathbb{S} & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$ over $X := \{i\}$.

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{\overline{3}} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (478)$$

$$q_X \left(\prod_{i=1}^{\overline{5}} i+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (479)$$

Lemma 3.40. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, the following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=\overline{P_{i=s}^{n_2}} t \end{array} \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1+n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right). \quad (480)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$, $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. Assert $n_1 = 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=\overline{P_{i=s}^{n_2}} t \end{array} \right) \quad (481)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1=0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right) \quad (482)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1=0}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1+n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right). \quad (483)$$

Now assert $n_1 > 0$. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=\overline{P_{i=s}^{n_2}} t \end{array} \right) \stackrel{n_1>0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=(i) \end{array} \right) \underbrace{\text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right) \right]}_{=:u}. \quad (484)$$

It is left to show the equality $u = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1+n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right)$ (hereinafter referred to as the subclaim). Assert $n_2 = 0$. Then holds:

$$u \stackrel{(484)}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=(i) \end{array} \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right) \right] \quad (485)$$

$$\stackrel{n_2=0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=(i) \end{array} \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (486)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1>0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right) \quad (487)$$

$$\stackrel{n_2=0}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1+n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right). \quad (488)$$

Now assert $n_2 > 0$ and assume that the subclaim has already been proven for $n_2 - 1$. Note that this assumption encompasses the truth of the subclaim for any $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, in particular for (i) . Thus follows:

$$u \stackrel{(484)}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=(i) \end{array} \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i=s \end{array} \right) \right] \quad (489)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \stackrel{\substack{n_2 > 0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=(i)}^{n_1-1} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \\ & \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=(i)}^{n_2-1} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (490)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.12}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=(i)}^{n_1-1} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=(i)}^{n_2-1} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \right] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (491)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.12}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=(i)}^{n_1-1} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X \left[i \mapsto q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=(i)}^{n_2-1} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (492)$$

$$= q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=(i)}^{n_1+n_2-1} t \right) \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (493)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n_1+n_2 > 0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s}^{n_1+n_2} t \right). \quad (494)$$

□

We may now generalize to arbitrary degrees of nesting and observe that recursion operators over the same variable nested in their respective start values collapse to a single recursion operator with the sum of recursion depths as the new recursion depth.

Theorem 3.41. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=\dots \overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s}^{n_k} t}^{n_2} t}^{n_1} t \right) = q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s}^{\sum_{j=1}^k n_j} t \right). \quad (495)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$. For $n = 1$ the claim is trivial, and for $n = 2$ it is equivalent to Lemma 3.40. Assert $n > 2$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for $n - 1$. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=\dots \overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s}^{n_k} t}^{n_2} t}^{n_1} t \right) \quad (496)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.20}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ \vdots \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s} \end{array} t \end{array} \right) \end{array} \right) \quad (497)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=q_X \left(\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{\sum_{j=2}^k n_j} t \end{array} \right) \end{array} \right) \quad (498)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.20}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{\sum_{j=2}^k n_j} t \end{array} \right) \quad (499)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.40}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=s \end{array} \right) \quad (500)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=s \end{array} \right). \quad (501)$$

□

We conclude that all of the neat properties of sums must also apply to nested recursion operators. In particular, the nested recursion depths are commutative and we may permute them in any way. We will use symmetric groups to capture the concept of commutativity.

Corollary 3.42. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i \in X$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $\pi \in S_k$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s} \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s} \end{array} t \right). \quad (502)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i \in X$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $\pi \in S_k$. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i=s} \end{array} t \right) \quad (503)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Theorem 3.41}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i=s \end{array} \right) \quad (504)$$

$$= q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i=s}^{\sum_{j=1}^k n_{\pi(j)}}} t \right) \quad (505)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Theorem 3.41}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i=\overline{P_{i=s}^{n_{\pi(1)}}}}^{\overline{P_{i=s}^{n_{\pi(2)}}}} \dots \overline{P_{i=s}^{n_{\pi(k)}}} t} \right). \quad (506)$$

□

The next lemma provides a technical detail necessary to prove the last theorem, namely Theorem 3.46.

Lemma 3.43. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_2\})$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i_1=(i_2)}^{\overline{n}}} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] = q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i_1=s}^{\overline{n}}} t \right). \quad (507)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_2\})$. Assert $n = 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i_1=(i_2)}^{\overline{n}}} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (508)$$

$$\stackrel{n=0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X((i_2)) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (509)$$

$$\stackrel{(i_2) \in T(X)}{=} q_X|_{T(X)}((i_2)) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (510)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{Squ})}{=} (i_2) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (511)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3}), (\text{ApS1})}{=} q_X(s) \quad (512)$$

$$\stackrel{n=0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i_1=s}^{\overline{n}}} t \right). \quad (513)$$

Now assert $n > 0$. Thus follows:

$$q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i_1=(i_2)}^{\overline{n}}} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (514)$$

$$\stackrel{n>0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} \underbrace{q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i_1=(i_1)}^{\overline{n-1}}} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)]}_{(515)} \quad (515)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} \overbrace{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)]} \left(\underbrace{q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{i_1=(i_1)}^{\overline{n-1}}} t \right)}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i_2\}) \\ \text{Lemma 3.17}}} \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (516)$$

$$= \overbrace{\text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)]}_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_2\})} \left(q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (517)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.13}}{=} \overbrace{\text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)]}_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_2\})} \left(q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (518)$$

$$\stackrel{(\text{ApS3})}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (519)$$

$$\stackrel{t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_2\})}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_2\})}(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (520)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} \underbrace{q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto \underbrace{q_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}(t)}_{\in T(X \setminus \{i_2\})}]}_{\substack{\in T(X \setminus \{i_2\}) \\ \text{Lemma 2.7}}} \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto (i_2)] \text{en}_X[i_2 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (521)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.15}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto q_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (522)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.13}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto q_X|_{T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_2\})}(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (523)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_{X \setminus \{i_2\}}[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (524)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.13}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)]|_{X \setminus \{i_2\}} \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (525)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n-1} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(t)] \text{en}_X[i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (526)$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{n>0 \\ (\text{StS3})}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=s \end{array} t \right). \quad (527)$$

□

As of before, we first prove the statement of the main theorem for a single nested recursion operator.

Example 3.44. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be the term algebra of type $\left(\{0, 1, S, +\}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & S & + \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$ over $X := \{i, j\}$.

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{2} \quad \overline{3} \\ \mathbf{P} \mathbf{P} \\ i=1 \quad j=i \end{array} j+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (528)$$

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{6} \\ \mathbf{P} \\ j=1 \end{array} j+1 \right) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \quad (529)$$

Lemma 3.45. For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$, the following equation holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{cc} \overline{n_1} & \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} & \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_1=s & i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1 \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=s \end{array} t \right). \quad (530)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $i_1, i_2 \in X$ with $i_1 \neq i_2$, $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1\})$. Assert $n_1 = 0$. Then holds:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{cc} \overline{n_1} & \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} & \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_1=s & i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \quad (531)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1=0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X(s) \quad (532)$$

$$\stackrel{0 \cdot n_2=0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{0 \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=s \end{array} t \right) \quad (533)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1=0}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1 \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=s \end{array} t \right). \quad (534)$$

Now assert $n_1 > 0$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for $n_1 - 1$. Thus follows:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{cc} \overline{n_1} & \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} & \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_1=s & i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \quad (535)$$

$$\stackrel{n_1 > 0}{\stackrel{(\text{StS3})}{=}} q_X \left(\begin{array}{cc} \overline{n_1-1} & \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} & \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_1=(i_1) & i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i_1 \mapsto q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (536)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{(n_1-1) \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i_1 \mapsto q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \right] \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \quad (537)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.12}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{(n_1-1) \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i_1 \mapsto q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X [i_1 \mapsto q_X(s)] \right] \quad (538)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.43}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{(n_1-1) \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=(i_1) \end{array} t \right) \text{en}_X \left[i_1 \mapsto q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=s \end{array} t \right) \right] \quad (539)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.43}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{(n_1-1) \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=\overline{\mathbf{P}}_{i_2=s} t \end{array} t \right) \quad (540)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.40}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{(n_1-1) \cdot n_2 + n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=s \end{array} t \right) \quad (541)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1 \cdot n_2} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ i_2=s \end{array} t \right). \quad (542)$$

□

Thus follows the general case, stating that "chained" recursion operators collapse to a single recursion operators with the product of recursion depths as the new recursion depth.

Theorem 3.46. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $i_1, \dots, i_k \in X$, where i_1, \dots, i_k are distinct, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\})$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \quad \overline{n_2} \quad \dots \quad \overline{n_k} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \dots \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1}) \end{array} \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\prod_{j=1}^k n_j} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_k=s \end{array} \right). \quad (543)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $i_1, \dots, i_k \in X$, i_1, \dots, i_k be distinct, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\})$. For $n = 1$, the claim is trivial, and for $n = 2$ it is equivalent to Lemma 3.45. Assert $n > 2$ and assume that the claim has already been proven for $n - 1$. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \quad \overline{n_2} \quad \dots \quad \overline{n_k} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \dots \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1}) \end{array} \right) \quad (544)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.21}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_2} \quad \dots \quad \overline{n_k} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \dots \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1}) \end{array} \right) \\ i_1=s \end{array} \right) \quad (545)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\prod_{j=2}^k n_j} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_k=(i_1) \end{array} \right) \\ i_1=s \end{array} \right) \quad (546)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.21}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \quad \overline{\prod_{j=2}^k n_j} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_1=s \quad i_k=(i_1) \end{array} \right) \quad (547)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Lemma 3.45}}{=} q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1 \cdot \prod_{j=2}^k n_j} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_k=s \end{array} \right) \quad (548)$$

$$= q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{\prod_{j=1}^k n_j} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_k=s \end{array} \right). \quad (549)$$

□

Again, the recursion depths commute.

Corollary 3.47. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $i_1, \dots, i_k \in X$, where i_1, \dots, i_k are distinct, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\})$ and $\pi \in S_k$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \quad \overline{n_2} \quad \dots \quad \overline{n_k} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \dots \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1}) \end{array} \right) = q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_{\pi(1)}} \quad \overline{n_{\pi(2)}} \quad \dots \quad \overline{n_{\pi(k)}} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \dots \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1}) \end{array} \right). \quad (550)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $i_1, \dots, i_k \in X$, i_1, \dots, i_k be distinct, $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$, $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\})$ and $\pi \in S_k$. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\begin{array}{c} \overline{n_1} \quad \overline{n_2} \quad \dots \quad \overline{n_k} \\ \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad \dots \quad \overline{\mathbf{P}} \quad t \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1}) \end{array} \right) \quad (551)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Theorem 3.46}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{j=1}^k n_j} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \\ i_k=s}} t \quad (552)$$

$$= q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{j=1}^k n_{\pi(j)}} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \\ i_k=s}} t \quad (553)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Theorem 3.46}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{n_{\pi(1)}} \overline{n_{\pi(2)}} \dots \overline{n_{\pi(k)}} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \quad \mathbf{P} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1})}} t. \quad (554)$$

□

Lastly, we consider a special case where all of the recursion depths are the same. The recursion depth of the collapsed recursion operator can then obviously be expressed through exponentiation.

Corollary 3.48. *For every recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $i_1, \dots, i_k \in X$, where i_1, \dots, i_k are distinct, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\})$, the following equation holds:*

$$q_X \left(\overline{n} \overline{n} \dots \overline{n} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \quad \mathbf{P} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1})}} t = q_X \left(\overline{n^k} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \\ i_k=s}} t. \quad (555)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $i_1, \dots, i_k \in X$, where i_1, \dots, i_k are distinct, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ and $t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X \setminus \{i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\})$. It follows:

$$q_X \left(\overline{n} \overline{n} \dots \overline{n} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \quad \mathbf{P} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{P} \\ i_1=s \quad i_2=(i_1) \quad \dots \quad i_k=(i_{k-1})}} t \quad (556)$$

$$\stackrel{\text{Theorem 3.46}}{=} q_X \left(\overline{\prod_{j=1}^k n} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \\ i_k=s}} t \quad (557)$$

$$= q_X \left(\overline{n^k} \right)_{\substack{\mathbf{P} \\ i_k=s}} t. \quad (558)$$

□

4 Applications and Examples

4.1 General considerations

In the following section, we are no longer interested in the actual terms themselves, but rather the values of these terms. Given a recursion operator extensible term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ over X , an algebra \mathbf{A} of the same type, whose universe we call A , and an assignment $\varphi: X \rightarrow A$, we can determine the value of a term $t \in T(X)$ in \mathbf{A} by applying the homomorphism $\overline{\varphi}: \mathbf{T}(X) \rightarrow \mathbf{A}$ induced by φ to t , which yields $\overline{\varphi}(t)$. Now consider the recursion operator extension $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ and the value of a term $u \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ in the same algebra \mathbf{A} . Because $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ and \mathbf{A} are of different types, a homomorphism between them cannot exist, but this does not pose a problem, since we can express u uniquely as a

term in $\mathbf{T}(X)$ by applying the standard squashing q_X . Thus, the value of u in \mathbf{A} is determined by the composition $\bar{\varphi} \circ q_X : T_{\mathbf{P}}(X) \rightarrow A$.

We hereinafter take a term algebra $\mathbf{T}(X)$ and an algebra \mathbf{A} for granted, expecting them to obey the rules of standard arithmetic. Furthermore, we let $\varphi : X \rightarrow A$ be an arbitrary assignment, since we only consider terms $u \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ with $q_X(u) \in T(\emptyset)$, i.e. we will only utilize the variables in X for means of recursion.

Before taking a look at real applications of recursion operator extensions, it is helpful to define two short-hand notations for often occurring scenarios. The first one has to do with terms containing the recursion operator $\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{\bar{n}} t$, where s is a k -tuple with $k \in \mathbb{N}$. We are often only interested in the k -th element of the result, hence we agree upon the following notation.

Definition 4.1 (Short-hand notation for iterating over tuples). *Let $i \in X$ be a variable symbol, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $s \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ be a k -tuple and $t_1, \dots, t_k \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ be terms.*

$$q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{\bar{n}} \begin{array}{c} t_1 \\ \vdots \\ t_k \end{array} \right) := q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{\bar{n}} (t_1, \dots, t_k) \right)_k. \quad (\text{Dup})$$

The second one deals with converging sequences where the recursion depth is bounded to the sequence index. We use a similar notation as for the limits of series by omitting the lim operator and specifying ∞ as the recursion depth.

Definition 4.2 (Short-hand notation for limits of converging sequences). *Let $i \in X$ be a variable symbol, $s, t \in T_{\mathbf{P}}(X)$ be terms and $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be the sequence given by $a_n := \mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{\bar{n}} t$. If $(\bar{\varphi} \circ q_X(a_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges, we define:*

$$\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{\infty} t := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\varphi} \circ q_X(a_n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\varphi} \circ q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=s}^{\bar{n}} t \right). \quad (\text{Lim})$$

4.2 A simple example: Calculating the golden ratio

In order to give a quick example of a real application of the recursion operator, we aim to express the golden ratio Φ using the recursion operator. The golden ratio is defined as the unique real number $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}$ which solves the equation $\Phi = \frac{1}{1+\Phi}$. Let $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ be a sequence in \mathbb{R} which is defined recursively as follows:

$$a_0 := 1 \quad (559)$$

$$a_{n+1} := \frac{1}{1 + a_n}. \quad (560)$$

Obviously, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = \Phi$. The proof for this has already been presented numerous times and is not important for the further course. Note that we can rewrite a_n using the recursion operator:

$$a_n = \bar{\varphi} \circ q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=1}^{\bar{n}} \frac{1}{1+i} \right). \quad (561)$$

This yields a new characterization of Φ :

$$\Phi = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\varphi} \circ q_X \left(\mathbf{P}_{i=1}^{\bar{n}} \frac{1}{1+\Phi} \right) \stackrel{(\text{Lim})}{=} \mathbf{P}_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1+i}. \quad (562)$$

4.3 Observations on "big operators" of ABELian monoids

Another beautiful example would be the generalization of already existing short-hand notations for incomplete terms, namely indexed "big operators" of ABELian monoids like \sum or \prod . Let (M, \star) be an ABELian monoid with neutral element 0_M . Given a term t in the variable i and two non-negative integers k, n , we often write $\bigstar_{i=k}^n t(i)$ instead of $t(k) \star t(k+1) \star \dots \star t(n)$. The latter incomplete term can be expressed through the recursion operator. For the sake of readability, we omit writing $\overline{\varphi} \circ q_X$ and assume it being applied to every term in this subsection. We will also leave out the overline over recursion depths; this is done to demonstrate how the recursion operator could be used in an application outside of universal algebra, where we are not interested in the technical aspects and details; abuse of notation is unavoidable, but reasonable. The key observation is that for any fixed k and any $n > k$, we may perform the following manipulation:

$$\bigstar_{i=k}^n t(i) = t(k) \star \bigstar_{i=k+1}^n t(i). \quad (563)$$

We have now rewritten our initial term using some previously calculated partial result – i.e. recursively. In the cases where $k < n$ does not apply, we observe:

$$k = n \implies \bigstar_{i=k}^n t(i) = t(k) = t(n) \quad (564)$$

$$k > n \implies \bigstar_{i=k}^n t(i) = 0_M \text{ per definitionem.} \quad (565)$$

Unfortunately, the recursion operator does not keep track of the index of the current iteration, but t depends on that index. We can solve this problem by leveraging Definition 4.1 and iterating over both the current index starting at k , which we increment with each iteration, and the current partial result starting at 0_M , to which we apply $t(i)$ with each iteration, where i denotes the index, at the same time. Thus, as our initial term, we choose $i = (k, 0_M)$, and as our recursively applied term, we choose $(i_1 + 1, i_2 \star t(i_1))$. Note that the order, in which the terms of the latter tuple are evaluated is irrelevant; following the definitions regarding the recursion operator strictly, we observe that the whole tuple is evaluated "at the same time". We could therefore swap the elements of $(k, 0_M)$ and $(i_1 + 1, i_2 \star t(i_1))$, respectively. However, because we will make use of the notation defined in (Tup), the final result will have the last index of the tuple, so that all other elements except for the last one can be discarded.

The last thing to be discussed is the recursion depth. Iterating "from k to n " means performing exactly as many iterations as there lie non-negative integers between k and n , including k and n , if $k \leq n$, which happens to be equal to $n - k + 1$ iterations. Otherwise, zero iterations are performed and the result is equal to 0_M (see (565)). If we set the recursion depth to be $\max\{n - k + 1, 0_M\}$, it behaves exactly as desired.

We conclude:

$$\bigstar_{i=k}^n t(i) = \prod_{i=(k, 0_M)}^{\max\{n-k+1, 0\}} \left[\begin{array}{l} i_1 + 1 \\ i_2 \star t(i_1) \end{array} \right]. \quad (566)$$

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List of Figures

1	Characteristic property of squashings between term algebras	9
2	Idempotency of squashings between term algebras	10
3	Characteristic property and idempotency of squashings between term algebras	10
4	Algebraic properties of substitutions	24
5	The $(2, 2)$ -category $\mathbf{Trm}(X)$	26
6	Squash and interpretation in recursion operator extended term algebras	26
7	Recursive flowchart diagram of the standard squashing	30
8	Iterative flowchart diagram of the standard squashing	44

List of Tables

1	Symbols used	3
2	Arrows used in diagrams	4

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